

PRO-CLIMATE

Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change

Project Acronym	PRO-CLIMATE
Project Name	Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change
Project Number	101137967
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D1-01-09 - Behavioural change and governance for systemic transformations towards climate resilience
Type of Action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Granting Authority	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA)
Project starting date	1 January 2024
Project end date	31 December 2026
Project duration	36 months

D2.2 Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan

(Version 1.1, 28/07/2025)

Disclaimer: *Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.*

Copyright message: ©PRO-CLIMATE Consortium, 2024. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Deliverable Number	D2.2	
Deliverable Name	D2.2 Living Lab pilot operational plan	
Work Package No	WP2	
Due Date (month)	M18 (June 2025)	
Submission Date	30 June 2025	
Lead Beneficiary	ATU	
Version	1.0	
Status	First version	
Author name(s)	Dr. Catalin Anton, Dr. Xu Liu	
Contributor(s)	All partners	
Reviewer(s)	Prof. Ann-Marie Nienaber (CU), Kindy Sandhu (CU)	Jose-Maria Sanz (CAR), Pilar Munoz (BAD)
Approved by	Iason Tamiakis (Tero)	
Keywords	Living Labs, Stakeholders, Engagement, co-design, co-creation	
Type	Report	
Dissemination level	PU - Public	

The **PRO-CLIMATE** Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1 COO	TERO MONOPROSOPI IKE	TERO	EL
2 BEN	ATLANTIC TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	ATU	IE
3 BEN	INSTITOUTO SYNETAIRISTIKIS IGESIAS KAI SYNERGASIAS ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	Co-op	EL
4 BEN	UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN	UiB	NO
5 BEN	UNIVERSITAET LEIPZIG	ULEI	DE
6 BEN	NORCE NORWEGIAN RESEARCH CENTRE AS	NORCE	NO
7 BEN	FUNDACION CARTIF	CARTIF	ES
8 BEN	DIPUTACION PROVINCIAL DE BADAJOZ	DB	ES
9 BEN	UNIWERSYTET GDANSKI	UG	PL
10 BEN	COVENTRY UNIVERSITY	CU	UK

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	12/03/2025	Xu Liu (ATU)	Template and ToC
0.2	25/04/2025	Catalin Anton (ATU)	First draft of D2.2
0.3	29/04/2025	Xu Liu (ATU)	Review and Feedback on the first draft of D2.2
0.4	08/05/2025	Catalin Anton (ATU)	Second draft of D2.2
0.5	11/05/2025	Xu Liu (ATU), Salem Gharbia (ATU)	Review and Feedback on the second draft of D2.2
0.6	21/05/2025	LL leaders	Feedback on the draft of D2.2
0.7	25/05/2025	Catalin Anton (ATU), Xu Liu (ATU)	Revise and adjust the draft based on the feedback
0.8	14/06/2025	Kindy Sanduh (CU), Ann-Marie Nienaber (CU), Jose Maria Sanz (CAR), Pillar Munoz (BAD)	Internal Review
0.9	27/06/2025	Catalin Anton (ATU)	Revision of D2.2
1.0	30/06/2025	Iason Tamiakis (Tero), Ilias Trochidis (Tero)	Check, format and submission

Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	5
LIST OF FIGURES.....	7
LIST OF TABLES	8
ABBREVIATIONS.....	9
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	10
1 INTRODUCTION	12
1.1 THE PRO-CLIMATE PROJECT	12
1.2 WP2 CONTRIBUTION TO THE PROJECT	12
1.3 THE ROLE OF THE POP IN THE PRO-CLIMATE PROJECT.....	14
1.4 TREATMENT OF CONTEXTUAL DATA AND USE OF ANNEXES.....	14
2 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	15
2.1 PROBLEM SPACE	16
2.2 SOLUTION SPACE	16
2.3 DEPLOYMENT SPACE	16
3 METHODOLOGY: CO-CREATE THE PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN	16
3.1 CO-CREATION APPROACH.....	17
3.2 CO-DESIGN APPROACH	18
3.3 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS	18
3.4 INTEGRATING KNOWLEDGE FROM OTHER WORK PACKAGES	19
4 GENERAL INTRODUCTION OF THE PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN STRUCTURE	20
4.1 PHASE 1: EMPATHISE & DEFINE	21
4.2 PHASE 2: IDEATE & CO-DESIGN	21
4.3 PHASE 3: PROTOTYPE & PILOT.....	21
4.4 PHASE 4: TEST & EVALUATE	22
5 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN.....	22
5.1 ROLES AND ACCOUNTABILITIES WITHIN THE LIVING LAB	22
5.2 RESPONSIBILITIES OF PRO-CLIMATE WORK PACKAGE LEADERS	23
5.3 IMPLEMENTATION TIMELINE	24
6 CONCLUSION	25
ANNEX 1 BADAJOZ REGION LIVING LAB PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN	26
INTRODUCTION	26
PHASE 1: EMPATHISE & DEFINE	26
<i>Contextual Diagnosis</i>	26
<i>Stakeholder Mapping</i>	27
Stakeholder Ecosystem and Functional Roles	27
Governance and Representation Challenges.....	28
Role in the POP Lifecycle.....	28
<i>Focal Action Situation (FAS)</i>	29
Territorial and Socio-Ecological Stressors.....	29
Opportunities for Co-Creation and Adaptation	29
Behavioural and Institutional Barriers.....	30
Stakeholder Co-Creation	30
Institutional Transformation	30
Behavioural Change	30
Local Empowerment.....	30
PHASE 2: IDEATE & CO-DESIGN	31
PHASE 3: PROTOTYPE & PILOT.....	32
PHASE 4: TEST & EVALUATE	33
CONCLUSION	34
ANNEX 2 LEIPZIG LIVING LAB PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN	35

D2.2 Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan

INTRODUCTION	35
PHASE 1: EMPATHISE & DEFINE	35
<i>Contextual Diagnosis</i>	35
<i>Stakeholder Mapping</i>	36
Stakeholder Landscape and Roles.....	36
Governance Characteristics	37
Challenges of Equity and Participation.....	37
Mapping Methodology	37
<i>Focal Action Situation (FAS)</i>	38
The Communication Gap as an Entry Point.....	38
Core Areas of Intervention.....	38
Systemic Framing	39
Institutional and Behavioural Barriers	39
PHASE 2: IDEATE & CO-DESIGN	40
<i>Outcomes and Transition to Phase 3</i>	41
PHASE 3: PROTOTYPE & PILOT.....	41
PHASE 4: TEST & EVALUATE	42
CONCLUSION	43
ANNEX 3 ZAKYNTHOS LIVING LAB PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN	45
INTRODUCTION	45
PHASE 1: EMPATHISE & DEFINE	45
<i>Contextual Diagnosis</i>	45
<i>Stakeholder Mapping</i>	46
<i>Focal Action Situation (FAS)</i>	47
PHASE 2: IDEATE & CO-DESIGN	48
<i>Objectives and Approach</i>	48
<i>Methodological Integration</i>	48
<i>Emerging Priorities and Thematic Focus</i>	49
<i>Outcomes and Next Steps</i>	49
PHASE 3: PROTOTYPE & PILOT.....	50
PHASE 4: TEST & EVALUATE	51
CONCLUSION	52
ANNEX 4 GDANSK LIVING LAB PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN	54
INTRODUCTION	54
PHASE 1: EMPATHISE & DEFINE	54
<i>Contextual Diagnosis</i>	54
<i>Stakeholder Mapping</i>	56
Identified Stakeholders and Their Roles.....	56
Methodology	57
Governance Structures and Interactions	57
Engagement Mechanisms	57
<i>Focal Action Situation (FAS)</i>	57
Entry Points for Co-Creation.....	57
Systemic Framing of the FAS	58
Behavioural and Institutional Barriers.....	58
PHASE 2: IDEATE & CO-DESIGN	59
<i>Key Insights and Emerging Priorities</i>	59
<i>Pilot Focus Areas</i>	59
<i>Outcomes and Next Steps</i>	60
PHASE 3: PROTOTYPE & PILOT.....	60
<i>Pilot Objectives and Priorities</i>	60
<i>Stakeholder Engagement and Roles</i>	60
<i>Focus Areas for Piloting</i>	61
<i>Strategic and Policy Alignment</i>	61
PHASE 4: TEST & EVALUATE	62
<i>Monitoring and Evaluation Approach</i>	62
<i>Outcomes and Long-Term Impact</i>	62
CONCLUSION	63
ANNEX 5 SLIGO LIVING LAB PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN	64

D2.2 Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan

INTRODUCTION	64
PHASE 1: EMPATHISE & DEFINE	64
<i>Contextual Diagnosis</i>	64
<i>Opportunities for Systemic Change</i>	65
<i>Stakeholder Mapping</i>	66
Identified Stakeholders and Their Roles.....	66
Governance Structures and Interdependencies	66
Methodology and Typology	66
<i>Focal Action Situation (FAS)</i>	67
Territorial and Socio-Ecological Stressors.....	67
Entry Points for Co-Creation and Adaptation	67
Systemic Framing and Theory of Change Alignment.....	67
Behavioural and Institutional Barriers.....	68
PHASE 2: IDEATE & CO-DESIGN	68
<i>Objectives of the Co-Design Process</i>	68
<i>Stakeholder Engagement and Methods</i>	69
<i>Emerging Themes and Pilot Focus Areas</i>	69
<i>Outcomes and Next Steps</i>	70
PHASE 3: PROTOTYPE & PILOT.....	70
<i>Pilot Strategy and Methodological Framing</i>	70
<i>Pilot Implementation Themes and Components</i>	71
<i>Institutional Roles and Change Agents</i>	71
<i>Monitoring and Adaptive Learning</i>	71
<i>Expected Outcomes and Policy Alignment</i>	72
PHASE 4: TEST & EVALUATE	72
CONCLUSION	73
ANNEX 6 BERGEN LIVING LAB PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN	74
INTRODUCTION	74
PHASE 1: EMPATHISE & DEFINE	74
<i>Contextual Diagnosis</i>	74
<i>Opportunities for Systemic Change</i>	75
<i>Stakeholder Mapping</i>	76
Identified Stakeholders and Their Roles.....	76
Governance Structures.....	76
Methodology and Typology	77
<i>Focal Action Situation (FAS)</i>	78
Territorial and Socio-Ecological Stressors.....	78
Systemic Framing and Strategic Entry Points	78
Behavioural and Institutional Barriers.....	79
PHASE 2: IDEATE & CO-DESIGN	79
<i>Objectives and Early Engagement</i>	80
<i>Methods and Emerging Themes</i>	80
<i>Behavioural and Governance Integration</i>	80
<i>Focus Areas Emerging from Co-Design</i>	80
<i>Outcomes and Next Steps</i>	81
PHASE 3: PROTOTYPE & PILOT.....	81
<i>Pilot Strategy and Concept Preparation</i>	82
<i>Looking Ahead: Modelling Tool and Stakeholder Activation</i>	82
<i>Outlook and Next Steps</i>	82
PHASE 4: TEST & EVALUATE	83
<i>Objectives and Focus Areas</i>	83
<i>Forward Outlook</i>	84
CONCLUSION	84
BIBLIOGRAPHY	85

List of Figures

FIGURE 1. LIVING LAB FUNCTIONALITY AS A TESTBED FOR SYSTEMIC CHANGE	13
FIGURE 2. LIVING LAB INTEGRATIVE FRAMEWORK (ADAPTED FROM MASTELIC, 2019)	15

FIGURE 3. FOUR-PHASE PROCESS OF THE PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN STRUCTURE.....	21
FIGURE 4: BADAJOZ LIVING LAB STAKEHOLDER MAPPING BASED ON QUADRUPLE HELIX MODEL	29
FIGURE 5: LEIPZIG LIVING LAB STAKEHOLDER MAPPING BASED ON QUADRUPLE HELIX MODEL	38
FIGURE 6. GDANSK LIVING LAB STAKEHOLDER MAPPING BASED ON QUADRUPLE HELIX MODEL	56
FIGURE 7. BERGEN LIVING LAB STAKEHOLDER MAPPING BASED ON THE QUADRUPLE HELIX MODEL	78

List of Tables

TABLE 1: WP2 CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE PRO-CLIMATE PROJECT	13
TABLE 2. KEY DESIGN FUNCTIONS OF EACH PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN (POP).....	14
TABLE 3. CO-CREATION PROCESS IN DEVELOPING THE PILOT OPERATIONAL PLAN	17
TABLE 4. TOOLS AND METHODS FOR INCLUSIVE STAKEHOLDER INPUT	18
TABLE 5. ROLES AND ACCOUNTABILITIES WITHIN THE LIVING LAB	22
TABLE 6. RESPONSIBILITIES OF PRO-CLIMATE WORK PACKAGE LEADERS	23
TABLE 7. IMPLEMENTATION TIMELINE	24
TABLE 8: KEY CONTEXTUAL CHALLENGES IN THE BADAJOZ LIVING LAB	26
TABLE 9: KEY DIMENSIONS FOR ADDRESSING BARRIERS IN THE BADAJOZ LIVING LAB	31
TABLE 10: FOCUS AREAS IDENTIFIED IN THE CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP	32
TABLE 11: PILOT IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY – KEY COMPONENTS.....	33
TABLE 12: MONITORING AND SCALING STRATEGY FOR THE BADAJOZ LIVING LAB	33
TABLE 13: KEY CONTEXTUAL CHALLENGES IN THE LEIPZIG LIVING LAB	35
TABLE 14: ADDRESSING KEY BARRIERS IN THE LEIPZIG LIVING LAB	39
TABLE 15. FOCUS AREAS CO-DEFINED IN THE LEIPZIG LIVING LAB	40
TABLE 16. LEIPZIG PILOT IMPLEMENTATION COMPONENTS	41
TABLE 17. EVALUATION AND SCALING FRAMEWORK FOR THE LEIPZIG LIVING LAB	43
TABLE 18. KEY CONTEXTUAL CHALLENGES IN THE ZAKYNTHOS LIVING LAB.....	46
TABLE 19. PILOT FOCUS AREAS EMERGING FROM THE ZAKYNTHOS LL CO-DESIGN PHASE	49
TABLE 20. PILOT IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY AND OPERATIONAL COMPONENTS FOR ZAKYNTHOS LL	50
TABLE 21. MONITORING, RISK MANAGEMENT, AND SCALING STRATEGY FOR THE ZAKYNTHOS LIVING LAB.....	51
TABLE 22. KEY CONTEXTUAL CHALLENGES IN THE GDAŃSK LIVING LAB	55
TABLE 23. KEY DIMENSIONS FOR ADDRESSING BARRIERS IN THE GDAŃSK LIVING LAB	58
TABLE 24. FOCUS AREAS EMERGING FROM THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS.....	59
TABLE 25. FOCUS AREAS AND PILOT ACTIONS IN THE GDAŃSK LIVING LAB	61
TABLE 26. MONITORING, RISK MANAGEMENT, AND SCALING STRATEGY FOR THE GDAŃSK LL.....	62
TABLE 27. KEY CONTEXTUAL CHALLENGES IN THE SLIGO LIVING LAB	64
TABLE 28. DIMENSIONS ADDRESSING BEHAVIOURAL AND INSTITUTIONAL BARRIERS IN THE SLIGO LIVING LAB	68
TABLE 29. FOCUS AREAS EMERGED FROM THE IDEATION PROCESS	69
TABLE 30. PILOT IMPLEMENTATION THEMES AND COMPONENTS – SLIGO LIVING LAB	71
TABLE 31. MONITORING, RISK MANAGEMENT, AND SCALING STRATEGY – SLIGO LIVING LAB	72
TABLE 32. KEY CONTEXTUAL CHALLENGES IN THE BERGEN LIVING LAB	75
TABLE 33. SUMMARY OF STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGED.....	77
TABLE 34. DIMENSIONS ADDRESSING KEY BARRIERS IN THE BERGEN LL	79
TABLE 35. FOCUS AREAS EMERGING FROM THE IDEATION PROCESS	80
TABLE 36. PILOT IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY AND KEY OPERATIONAL COMPONENTS.....	82
TABLE 37. MONITORING, RISK MANAGEMENT, AND SCALING STRATEGY FOR THE BERGEN LL.....	83

Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
LL	Living Lab
POP	Pilot Operational Plan
REA	European Research Executive Agency
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
THM	Triple Helix Model
WP	Work Package
QHM	Quadruple Helix Model

Executive summary

The current document includes Deliverable D2.2 – Pilot Operational Plans (POPs) of the Horizon Europe-funded PRO-CLIMATE project (*Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change*, Project No. 101137967). As a key output of Work Package 2 (WP2), led by Atlantic Technological University (ATU), this deliverable establishes the methodological and practical foundation for implementing Living Labs (LLs) across six European regions: Sligo (Ireland), Leipzig (Germany), Badajoz (Spain), Bergen (Norway), Gdańsk (Poland), and Zakynthos (Greece).

PRO-CLIMATE seeks to empower communities to adapt proactively to climate change by fostering behavioural change, social innovation, and systemic governance transformation. At its core lies the concept of the Living Lab—an inclusive, multi-stakeholder innovation ecosystem where adaptation strategies are co-created, piloted, and evaluated in real-world settings.

The Pilot Operational Plan (POP) is the main instrument through which this ambition is translated into action. It serves as a detailed roadmap that guides each Living Lab from initial stakeholder engagement and contextual diagnosis to co-design, prototyping, and testing of climate adaptation interventions. POPs are not static blueprints but dynamic, locally tailored strategies that embed community ownership, behavioural insights, and policy alignment into the climate resilience process.

Structure and Methodology

Each POP is structured around a four-phase iterative model adapted from design thinking and systems innovation practices:

1. Empathise & Define – Conduct in-depth environmental, institutional, and behavioural diagnostics to identify local climate challenges and focal action situations.
2. Ideate & Co-Design – Facilitate collaborative workshops to develop stakeholder-driven adaptation solutions using participatory tools such as scenario-building and behavioural mapping.
3. Prototype & Pilot – Implement selected interventions in real-life contexts with the support of Living Lab leaders and “change agents.”
4. Test & Evaluate – Measure impact through KPIs, gather stakeholder feedback, and align outputs with long-term policy and governance frameworks.

The methodology is co-creative and inclusive, engaging actors from the Quadruple Helix Model—public sector, private sector, academia, and civil society. The process involved multiple stages of data collection and validation, including baseline surveys, bilateral interviews, online and physical workshops, and integration of findings from other project Work Packages (especially WP3 on stakeholder dynamics and WP4 on behavioural change and good governance).

Integration and Implementation

The POP framework is deeply embedded within the overall project architecture. It connects with all major project activities and deliverables, ensuring that local experimentation informs regional, national, and EU-level policy development. Key interdependencies include:

- WP3: Stakeholder mapping and social-ecological system analysis;
- WP4: Development of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and behavioural change strategies;
- WP5: Modelling and stress-testing via the TransCliR policy sandbox tool;
- WP6: Translation of local insights into policy recommendations.

The preparation and implementation of the Pilot Operational Plans (POPs) is scheduled during the project period, with clear timelines and milestones outlined for each phase. However, it is important to clarify that implementation will formally begin after the finalisation of the POP documents, expected in Month 18 (June–July 2025). Task 2.2, which started in Month 6 (June 2024), was

initiated with preparatory activities, including workshops and bilateral meetings with stakeholders. These activities laid the groundwork for co-designing the POPs in alignment with the Living Lab frameworks. As such, while the POPs are now nearing readiness, the actual implementation phase is set to commence in the second half of 2025. The POPs also assign roles and responsibilities to Living Lab Leaders, Change Agents, and local stakeholders to ensure shared ownership, local leadership, and transparent governance.

Outcomes and Impact

The Pilot Operational Plans (POPs) developed within PRO-CLIMATE aim to be catalysts for systemic transformation in the face of climate change, moving beyond isolated adaptation actions toward sustainable, community-driven resilience. In line with Horizon Europe's ambition to advance knowledge and provide solutions in areas such as pathways to climate neutrality, climate change adaptation, and social science for climate action, the POPs are designed to:

- **Structured Action Plans:** POPs provide clear, step-by-step roadmaps to test, implement, and evaluate climate resilience strategies in real-life contexts.
- **Living Lab Implementation:** POPs operationalise the Living Lab approach by guiding the setup, coordination, and evaluation of activities across multiple sites.
- **Climate Resilience at Local and Regional Level:** By integrating local knowledge and scientific tools, POPs contribute to more robust and context-sensitive adaptation measures.
- **Replicable Models:** POPs result in tested frameworks and processes that can be scaled up or transferred to other regions and contexts across Europe.
- **Policy-Relevant Insights:** The experimentation and outcomes of POPs inform local and EU-level policy with real-world data and evidence.
- **Empowered Communities and Institutions:** POPs enhance the capacity of stakeholders to collaborate, decide, and act for long-term resilience and sustainability.

Through these plans, PRO-CLIMATE not only tests innovative interventions but also builds a culture of resilience, ensuring that communities become proactive agents of change. The POPs position each Living Lab to act as a catalyst of systemic transformation, linking grassroots innovation with European climate ambitions.

1 Introduction

1.1 The PRO-CLIMATE Project

PRO-CLIMATE (Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change) is a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action (Grant Agreement No. 101137967) funded by the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). The project is rooted in the recognition that behavioural and systemic change is essential to achieving climate resilience in European communities (ProClimate page - EU Portal, 2024).

The central objective of PRO-CLIMATE is to empower communities to proactively adapt to climate change by fostering social transformation through the identification of social tipping points and policy actions. These efforts aim to trigger systemic transitions in governance, behaviour, and policy at local and regional levels (ProClimate project website, 2024).

To achieve this, PRO-CLIMATE employs a systems-thinking approach, viewing communities as complex socio-ecological systems where interactions between environmental, institutional, and social drivers determine adaptive capacity (Nienaber et al., 2019; Nienaber et al., 2023). The project integrates co-creation methodologies, behavioural insights, and participatory governance to develop innovative adaptation strategies and foster a culture of resilience (Arnold & Wade, 2015; Puerari et al., 2018).

A cornerstone of the project is the establishment of six diverse Living Labs (LLs) located in Sligo (Ireland), Leipzig (Germany), Badajoz Region (Spain), Bergen (Norway), Gdańsk (Poland), and Zakynthos (Greece). These LLs serve as collaborative platforms for stakeholders across the quadruple helix model—public sector, private sector, academia, and civil society—to co-design, implement, and evaluate adaptive interventions tailored to local realities (Weiss, 1995).

By integrating scientific knowledge with local experience and stakeholder engagement, PRO-CLIMATE aims to catalyse meaningful change across Europe and contribute to the EU's broader climate and sustainability goals.

1.2 WP2 Contribution to the Project

Work Package 2 (WP2), titled “*Establishing and Operationalising Living Labs*”, plays a foundational role in the PRO-CLIMATE project. It provides the conceptual and operational backbone for implementing real-world experimental environments—Living Labs (LLs)—across six diverse European regions. WP2 is led by Atlantic Technological University (ATU) and supported by all the consortium partners, who contribute through stakeholder engagement, contextual analysis, and participatory design activities (Anton, et al., 2024).

The effective designing of the Pilot Operational Plans (POPs) relies on the collaborative efforts of all Work Package (WP) leaders. Each WP brings complementary expertise that informs and supports different phases of the POP process—from co-design to implementation, monitoring, and policy uptake. Close coordination ensures methodological coherence, smooth data flow, stakeholder engagement, and policy relevance. The POPs thus function not as isolated planning tools but as integrative mechanisms driving systemic change across Living Labs.

The core aim of WP2 is to design and implement Pilot Operational Plans (POPs) that establish the foundation for each Living Lab (LL) — inclusive, participatory innovation ecosystems. These POPs serve as the strategic setup phase, enabling the operational environment in which WP3 and WP4 can effectively work to foster behavioural change and good governance. WP2 not only facilitates the co-creation process but also ensures alignment across work packages by applying consistent definitions and methodologies. These LLs serve as open platforms for co-creation, enabling local stakeholders to collaboratively explore adaptation needs, define focal action situations, and test systemic solutions (Geels, 2002; Moore, 2017a; Ståhlbröst, 2012; Waddock, 2001). Figure 1 shows the living lab functionality in the project.

Figure 1. Living Lab Functionality as a Testbed for Systemic Change

Specifically, WP2 contributes to the PRO-CLIMATE project by (Table 1):

Table 1: WP2 Contributions to the PRO-CLIMATE Project

Contribution Area	Description
Baseline Assessments	Coordinating data collection and analysis on local climate challenges, institutions, behaviour, and stakeholder dynamics.
Facilitation of Co-Design Processes	Organising and supporting bilateral meetings, surveys, workshops, and feedback loops for participatory development.
Living Lab Framework Design	Designing and deploying a flexible LL framework adaptable to varied socio-ecological contexts.
Development of Pilot Operational Plans (POPs)	Producing structured POPs as practical guides for implementing, testing, and evaluating adaptation interventions.
Cross-Lab Learning and WP Integration	Supporting synergies with WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6, and facilitating mutual learning across Living Labs.
Policy and SDG Alignment	Ensuring LL actions are coherent with EU climate policy, regional strategies, and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Through WP2, PRO-CLIMATE transforms the Living Lab concept from a theoretical model into a practical, grounded mechanism for adaptive governance. It ensures that the LLs are not only operational but also resilient, inclusive, and capable of generating systemic insights that inform both local implementation and EU-wide policy dialogues (Eriksson et al., 2005; Schuurman & Tönurist, 2017a).

1.3 The Role of the POP in the PRO-CLIMATE Project

The **Pilot Operational Plan (POP)** is a critical output of WP2 and a central instrument in operationalising the PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab approach. It translates the project's conceptual framework and place-based insights into structured, actionable roadmaps for each of the six Living Labs. The POP acts as a bridge between strategic vision and on-the-ground experimentation (Eriksson et al., 2005), offering clear guidance on implementation, roles, timelines, and evaluation (Table 2).

Table 2. Key Design Functions of Each Pilot Operational Plan (POP)

Function	Description
Contextualisation of Climate Challenges	Synthesises local insights from stakeholder consultations, environmental analysis, and institutional diagnostics to tailor adaptation strategies.
Coordination of Co-Creation Processes	Structures ideation, prototyping, piloting, and evaluation phases based on the socio-ecological specificities of each Living Lab.
Structured Pathway for Experimentation	Details milestones, stakeholder roles (e.g., LL leaders, change agents), governance mechanisms, and communication strategies for local implementation.
Integration of Cross-WP Tools and Frameworks	Aligns with tools and insights from WP3 (stakeholder analysis), WP4 (governance), WP5 (social tipping points identification), and WP6 (policy recommendation).
Ensure sustainability of the living labs	Explore potentials to ensure the long-term running of the living labs.

The POP also serves as a **shared reference point** for all actors involved in the Living Lab, promoting transparency, coordination, and mutual accountability. Its modular structure—organized around the four phases of the Living Lab process: *Empathise & Define, Ideate & Co-design, Prototype & Pilot, Test & Evaluate*—ensures clarity and comparability across different LLs while allowing for local customisation (Fischer, 2000; Reed, 2008).

The POP is introduced after the foundational elements of each Living Lab—such as defining the Focal Action Situation (FAS) and initial stakeholder engagement—are in place. It acts as a bridge between early co-design phases and structured implementation. Ultimately, the POP serves as a practical roadmap that translates shared ambition into coordinated action. It not only guides each Living Lab in implementing tailored climate adaptation solutions but also empowers communities to co-develop new governance practices, behavioural shifts, and policy pathways that underpin systemic resilience. (Friedman & Miles, 2010; McKenzie-Mohr, 2011).

1.4 Treatment of Contextual Data and Use of Annexes

Each Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan can be found in the annexes of this document. These annexes offer preliminary contextual analysis and stakeholder insights to support the co-design of adaptation actions under the Horizon Europe PRO-CLIMATE project. The information provided here reflects a combination of desk research, local consultations, and LL leader expertise conducted during the early stages of project implementation.

We acknowledge that some of the content, particularly regarding socio-environmental trends and governance challenges, is based on local perceptions and has not yet been fully validated by academic literature or triangulated through multiple data sources. These insights are nonetheless considered critical for initiating participatory processes, identifying leverage points, and framing the first iteration of Living Lab activities.

In line with the internal review and coordination feedback, this annex and the other LL-specific annexes should be interpreted as **working documents**. They are intended to inform D2.2 in a **summarized form**, with selected and verified insights incorporated into the main body of the deliverable. A more comprehensive and enriched version of these annexes will be **revisited and validated throughout the lifetime of the project**, incorporating stakeholder feedback, empirical evidence from pilot activities, and cross-LL learning.

The **final, extended versions** of each LL annex—refined through iterative engagement and supplemented by monitoring data—will be included in **Deliverable D2.3 (due in Month 34)**. D2.3 will consolidate validated results, lessons learned, and policy recommendations, providing a robust and well-documented output grounded in both participatory evidence and scholarly research.

This process ensures that local voices are captured early while safeguarding the scientific and policy credibility of the project’s outputs. As the LL evolves, these annexes will remain as living documents, open to iterative refinement and stakeholder co-authorship.

2 Conceptual Framework

To operationalise climate resilience through social transformation, the PRO-CLIMATE project adopts a **systemic Living Lab (LL) framework** grounded in behavioural science, governance innovation, and co-creation methodologies. The conceptual framework that underpins each Pilot Operational Plan (POP) is designed to accommodate the diversity of socio-ecological contexts (Amorim et al., 2022; Baccarne et al., 2016; Ballon et al., 2015; Marvin et al., 2018).

This chapter introduces the structure through which each Living Lab processes from problem exploration to tested solutions. The framework is organised into three interlinked domains—**Problem Space, Solution Space, and Deployment Space**—which together enable a flexible, iterative, and participatory approach to climate adaptation (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Living Lab Integrative Framework (adapted from Mastelic, 2019)

2.1 Problem Space

The **Problem Space** represents the first step in each Living Lab's journey and focuses on understanding the local context, identifying system vulnerabilities, and defining the *focal action situations (FAS)*. Through this diagnostic phase, each LL explores, together with WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 environmental, social, and institutional challenges using tools such as stakeholder mapping, power-interest matrices, baseline assessments, and participatory discussions (Amorim et al., 2022; Calzada & Cowie, 2017; Marvin et al., 2018).

Key objectives of this phase:

- Establish a shared understanding of local climate risks and socio-political barriers.
- Identify behavioural patterns and institutional gaps that impede adaptation.
- Define focal action situations
- Define systemic leverage points and social tipping elements relevant to the region.

Outputs from this space include contextual diagnosis reports, stakeholder maps using the Quadruple Helix Model, and preliminary focal areas for intervention.

2.2 Solution Space

The **Solution Space** focuses on ideation, design, and prototyping of interventions that respond to the challenges defined in the Problem Space. It is characterised by iterative co-design activities involving LL stakeholders, including citizens, researchers, public authorities, and local organisations. The use of Living Lab methods such as scenario-building, visioning workshops, and behavioural mapping enables the formulation of actionable, place-based solutions (Arnold & Wade, 2015; Brown, 2009; Wright et al., 2012).

Core features include:

- Stakeholder-driven solution design and prioritisation.
- Application of behaviour change strategies and adaptive governance models.

This phase produces co-designed interventions, pilot action plans, and evaluation criteria, with a substantial contribution from WP3 and WP4.

2.3 Deployment Space

The **Deployment Space** centres on the piloting, testing, and evaluation of the designed interventions in real-world conditions. It is where Living Labs, together with other WPs insights, especially WP5, move from planning to action, ensuring that insights are not only validated but also refined based on feedback. This phase includes implementation protocols, role allocation (e.g. Living Lab leaders, change agents), risk management plans, and performance monitoring systems aligned with WP6 (Arnold & Wade, 2015; Brown, 2009).

Key aspects include:

- Pilot implementation with stakeholder participation and institutional support.
- Monitoring of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and behavioural impacts.
- Evaluation and learning loops to inform iterative improvements.

The outcomes from this space feed directly into project-level policy recommendations, replication strategies, and cross-Lab learning.

3 Methodology: Co-Create the Pilot Operational Plan

The development of each **Pilot Operational Plan (POP)** follows a co-creation methodology that combines structured design thinking with iterative, place-based engagement. This chapter outlines

the multi-step process used across all Living Labs (LLs) to build their POPs, highlighting data collection tools, stakeholder collaboration strategies, and validation mechanisms (Ballon et al., 2015; Compagnucci et al., 2021).

The methodology is participatory, flexible, and grounded in the **Living Lab Integrative Framework** introduced in Deliverable D2.1.

3.1 Co-Creation Approach

In the PRO-CLIMATE project, **co-creation** is not simply a tool, but a guiding principle that shapes how Living Labs (LLs) engage with climate adaptation. It is understood as a process that, based on identified needs, develops shared results by activating **knowledge flows and absorptive capacities** from all relevant actors across the economic and social spectrum (Commission, 2016)

In this context, **co-creation is the outcome of an evolving process** in which diverse forms of knowledge, values, and expertise come together to build a **consistent and sustainable Living Lab** ecosystem. The aim is to ensure that interventions are not only technically effective but also socially legitimate and owned by the communities they serve. (Committee of the Regions. Commission for Social Policy Education et al., 2016; Freeman, 2004)

This process was implemented across five structured steps, each aligned with the Living Lab development framework (Table 3).

Table 3. Co-Creation Process in Developing the Pilot Operational Plan

Step	Title	Description
Step 1	Baseline Assessment	Analysis of environmental, social, and institutional contexts through desk research, fieldwork, and stakeholder mapping using the Quadruple Helix Model.
Step 2	Stakeholder Engagement	Strategic engagement via bilateral meetings, surveys, and interviews to identify risks, gaps in trust, governance issues, and behavioural opportunities.
Step 3	Co-Creation Workshops	Two-day workshops: Day 1 for internal planning and Day 2 for stakeholder co-design of actions, conducted in local language and using participatory tools.
Step 4	Synthesis and Drafting	Workshop results synthesised into draft POPs, balancing local specificity with methodological coherence across Living Labs.
Step 5	Validation and Feedback	Draft POPs reviewed by stakeholders and consortium partners, enabling refinement and strategic alignment with WPs 2, 3, 4, and 6.

Co-Creation Enablers and Barriers

As identified by (Friedman & Miles, 2010), the success of co-creation depends heavily on both organisational and societal factors. These must be carefully managed to maintain inclusivity and momentum.

To Be Encouraged:

- Compatibility of public organisations with citizen participation
- Open attitudes toward engagement
- Clear incentives for collaboration
- Citizen awareness and sense of ownership
- Strong social capital
- Inclusive and transparent communication

To Be Avoided:

- Risk-averse, conservative administrative cultures
- Citizen aversion due to unclear roles or past exclusion

3.2 Co-Design approach

Co-design is a participatory approach that places citizens at the very centre of the development process, ensuring that the solutions created reflect their needs, values, and lived experiences. Unlike traditional consultation, which often limits engagement to feedback, co-design actively **empowers stakeholders as equal contributors** throughout the entire cycle of problem framing, ideation, and solution development (McKenzie-Mohr, 2011; Sanders & Stappers, 2008).

According to (Freeman, 2004), *co-design enables a wide range of people to make a creative contribution in the formulation and solution of a problem*. It does so by fostering **collaborative environments** in which citizens affected by a specific issue engage in the design process not as passive recipients but as **co-creators of change**. This dynamic leads to more relevant, accepted, and sustainable solutions.

A fundamental principle of co-design is the recognition of users as *"experts of their own experience."* Their insights are essential in surfacing hidden barriers, generating innovative ideas, and ensuring the cultural and social appropriateness of interventions. In the context of the PRO-CLIMATE project, this means that local communities—farmers, youth, cooperatives, educators, small businesses, and vulnerable groups—could be all engaged as **co-designers of climate adaptation strategies** (Schoorman & Tönurist, 2017b; Thorne et al., 2009; Tomaszewski et al., 2020).

In the Living Labs established under PRO-CLIMATE, co-design was embedded through:

- **Inclusive Workshops:** Facilitated sessions that combined creative tools, storytelling, and scenario planning.
- **Iterative Feedback Loops:** Ensuring ongoing refinement of ideas and recognition of evolving needs.
- **Multilingual Facilitation:** Reducing communication barriers and supporting participation across different literacy and digital access levels.
- **Equal Power Sharing:** Encouraging balanced dialogue between institutional stakeholders and community members.

By institutionalising co-design, the PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs move beyond tokenistic participation. They create **spaces of trust and innovation** that foster joint ownership of climate resilience pathways—building not only better solutions but also stronger communities.

3.3 Data Collection and Analysis

Multiple tools and methods (Table 4) were used to ensure comprehensive, inclusive, and representative input:

Table 4. Tools and Methods for Inclusive Stakeholder Input

Tool / Method	Purpose
Online Questionnaire	An online survey was conducted at the beginning of the project to understand the baseline of each living labs, including gathering stakeholder perceptions, adaptation priorities, and identifying perceived barriers. The results of the baseline assessment are presented in D2.1.
Bilateral Meetings	Two bilateral meetings were conducted for each living labs respectively to understand the development status of the living labs and to help the living lab leaders solving encountered challenges. It enabled deeper exploration of institutional challenges and engagement dynamics through focused, small-group dialogue.

Online workshops	One online workshop was conducted for each of the living labs respectively. It aimed to validate the baseline assessment results with the living lab core team and to further identify key stakeholder groups (power-interest matrix), to identify opportunities and barriers (SWOT analysis), and to depict a long-term vision (imagining a positive future).
Participatory Physical Workshops	<p>Two days physical workshops were conducted for each living labs respectively. We (WP2) facilitated the first day workshop with the living lab core teams followed a general agenda (see in annex x) applied for all the living labs, which aims to understand the local context (culture, socioeconomics, democracy, politics, social dynamic, etc.), local climate issues, and the past implemented climate solutions.</p> <p>For the second day workshop, we adopted a unique individual approach for each living labs, which means every living lab has it own different workshop agenda (see in annex x) based on its own living lab status as well ran by its local language. We came up with this approach based the previous discussions during the bilateral meetings and online workshops with the living lab leaders and the other WPLs. It aims to integrate diverse local stakeholders and to mitigate the potential language barriers in the co-creation process.</p>
Monitoring and Assessment Preparation	Two multilateral meetings led by WP4, together with WP2, WP3, and WP5 were conducted to identified Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Living Lab governance monitoring and assessments. Furthermore, one bilateral meeting was conducted with WP4 to decide the audit measures for the KPIs. The results are presented in D4.2.

Each data source was triangulated to ensure accuracy, inclusiveness, and contextual sensitivity.

3.4 Integrating Knowledge from Other Work Packages

The methodology explicitly incorporated outputs and expertise from other PRO-CLIMATE work packages, especially considerable contributions from WP3 and WP4:

- **WP3** provided insights and guidance on analysing social ecological system in each LL, identifying focal action situation and key stakeholders, which aims to identify key drivers for systemic transformation and community-led adaptation. A major contribution is **Deliverable D3.2: Comprehensive Stakeholder Analysis**, which provides a detailed examination of governance structures, power dynamics, and engagement challenges across the six Living Labs. The analysis applied Ostrom's Social-Ecological Systems Framework (SESF) to classify stakeholders, assess influence and legitimacy, and identify barriers to inclusive engagement. By mapping formal and informal roles and interdependencies, D3.2 offers actionable insights into how stakeholder configurations can enable or constrain climate adaptation. This directly informs the POP's approach to local governance, stakeholder engagement, and institutional design.
- **WP4** contributed governance frameworks, institutional typologies, and practical tools to support behavioural change and local capacity building. WP4 (together with WP3 and WP2) developed **Deliverable 4.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** to Measure Changes in Capacity with Respect to Climate Resilience. Mandatory and Optional KPIs have been produced to track and assess climate resilience progress within each Living Lab (LL). These KPIs are structured around 4 key governance themes as shown below:

1. **Governance Structure:** Focuses on the engagement and efficiency of both formal and informal governance bodies, including how they encourage behavioural change through inclusive participation and community-driven initiatives.

2. Governance Processes: Evaluates decision-making inclusiveness, transparency, collaboration, and adherence to established norms, emphasizing processes that motivate behavioural shifts toward proactive climate adaptation.
3. Governance Culture: Measures community values, informal practices, inclusiveness, and shared norms that influence behavioural change and promote climate-resilient practices.
4. Governance Outcomes: Assesses the real-world impact of governance efforts, adaptability to climate challenges, resilience, and learning capacity, including the extent to which behavioural changes contribute to sustainable governance improvements.

The KPIs serve as tools for reflection, adjustment, and learning, supporting both short-term and long-term impacts; the former crucial for tracking immediate improvements and the latter for tracking sustainability of governance mechanisms and overall resilience of communities to climate impacts..

Together, WP3 and WP4 bring a complementary understanding of *who* needs to be involved, *how* they should be engaged, and *what* success looks like, shaping a methodology that is both scientifically grounded and socially responsive. This integration reinforces the co-creation approach, making the POP a robust, inclusive, and action-oriented strategy for local climate resilience.

4 General Introduction of the Pilot Operational Plan Structure

The **Pilot Operational Plan (POP)** is the core strategic document for each Living Lab (LL) under the PRO-CLIMATE project. It offers a structured yet flexible roadmap for how each LL will progress through the design, implementation, and evaluation of climate adaptation interventions, with a strong emphasis on behavioural change, stakeholder engagement, and systemic transformation.

Each POP follows a consistent structure, organised into **four distinct but interconnected phases** that reflect the adapted Living Lab integrative process proposed in Deliverable D2.1 (Figure 3). This process draws inspiration from human-centred design thinking and the (Moore, 2017b) framework, while integrating systemic tools from governance and behavioural sciences.

Figure 3. Four-Phase Process of the Pilot Operational Plan Structure

4.1 Phase 1: Empathise & Define

This initial phase involves developing a comprehensive understanding of the local context. It includes:

- Environmental and socio-political diagnosis;
- Stakeholder mapping using the Quadruple Helix Model;
- Identification of focal action situations (FAS);
- Definition of behavioural and institutional barriers.

The objective is to establish shared evidence base and problem framing that is grounded in local realities and co-owned by stakeholders.

4.2 Phase 2: Ideate & Co-Design

In this phase, stakeholders collaborate to develop and prioritise solutions. Activities include:

- Visioning and scenario-building exercises;
- Brainstorming and prioritisation of interventions;
- Behavioural mapping and leverage point identification.

Outputs of this phase include a portfolio of co-designed actions and a defined pathway for the Living Lab implementation.

4.3 Phase 3: Prototype & Pilot

This stage focuses on translating ideas into tangible interventions. It involves:

- Piloting selected solutions in real-world settings;
- Continuing to mobilise local actors, including change agents and pilot-associated partners;
- Developing pilot protocols and coordination mechanisms.

This phase validates the technical, social, and political feasibility of proposed actions.

4.4 Phase 4: Test & Evaluate

The final phase centres on testing the effectiveness and scalability of the interventions. Activities include:

- Stakeholder feedback loops and reflective sessions;
- Measurement of KPIs related to behavioural shifts, governance innovation, and social learning (the detailed information about the selection and the measurements of the KPIs are presented in D4.2 KPIs to Measure Changes in Capacity with Respect to Climate Resilience);
- Adjustments based on real-time learning;
- Strategic alignment monitoring & assessment of the activities and WP6 policy recommendations.

This phase ensures that interventions are not only tested but positioned for long-term adoption, replication, and policy influence.

5 Implementation of the Pilot Operational Plan

This chapter outlines how the Pilot Operational Plan (POP) will be implemented in practice across the Living Labs. It defines the **roles and responsibilities**, coordination mechanisms, and implementation timeline needed to ensure effective delivery of co-created climate adaptation strategies. The POP is designed not only as a roadmap for local experimentation but also as a **living governance tool** that promotes ownership, accountability, and flexibility among stakeholders.

5.1 Roles and Accountabilities within the Living Lab

To ensure effective implementation and governance of each Living Lab, the PRO-CLIMATE project defines clear roles and responsibilities across three key actor groups: **Living Lab Leaders**, **Change Agents**, and **Stakeholders**. Table 5 outlines the distinct functions and contributions of each group within the co-creation and operational framework of the Pilot Operational Plan.

Table 5. Roles and accountabilities within the Living Lab

Actor	Role	Key Responsibilities
Living Lab Leaders	Coordinate the overall implementation and strategic alignment of the Living Lab.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oversee day-to-day implementation of the POP - Facilitate stakeholder communication - Report progress and barriers to WP2 - Ensure alignment with project-wide objectives
Change Agents	Act as local catalysts of transformation and engagement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the behavioural change - Bridge dialogue between citizens, institutions, and partners - Identify the tipping points

		- Facilitate feedback during pilots and evaluations
Living Lab Stakeholders	Represent the quadruple helix (public, private, academic, civil society) and co-create solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-design and pilot interventions - Provide local insights and expertise - Test and validate solutions - Engage in governance and monitoring activities

5.2 Responsibilities of PRO-CLIMATE Work Package Leaders

Implementation of the POP requires close coordination with other WPs to ensure methodological coherence, data flow, and policy relevance (Table 6)

Table 6. Responsibilities of PRO-CLIMATE Work Package Leaders

Work Package	Main Focus	Responsibilities
WP2 – Living Lab Approach for Co-creation (Lead: ATU)	Operational coordination of Living Labs (LLs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design and contextualise the Living Lab framework for each site. - Develop and coordinate Pilot Operational Plans (POPs). - Oversee day-to-day implementation and evaluation of LL activities. - Ensure knowledge production, exchange, and sustainability planning.
WP3 – Mapping of Climate Change Adaptation Systems (Lead: Co-op)	Social-ecological system analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define the boundaries of the social-ecological system for each LL. - Identify focal action situations and key drivers of change. - Map stakeholders using the Ostromean Framework. - Develop adaptation strategies and support WP2 contextualisation.
WP4 – Good Governance and Behavioural Change (Lead: CU)	Behavioural transformation and governance innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build capacity for behavioural and institutional change. - Develop change visions and toolkits. - Support LLs in implementing systemic transformation processes. - Promote learning communities through stakeholder engagement.
WP5 – Modelling and Stress Testing the System (Lead: UiB)	System modelling and stress testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a conceptual model and a Multi-Agent Computer Model (MACM). - Identify social tipping and leverage points for transformation. - Develop the TransCliR policy sandbox tool for scenario testing.

		- Validate modelling through LL data and feedback.
WP6 – Policy Recommendations (Lead: ULEI)	Policy translation and upscaling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate LL and MACM results to identify actionable policy areas. - Conduct policy workshops with stakeholders. - Deliver concise, context-specific policy briefs. - Bridge project outcomes with regional, national, and EU policy frameworks.

Cross-WP integration ensures the POP is not a siloed activity but part of a **multi-level strategy for systemic transformation**.

5.3 Implementation Timeline

The Pilot Operational Plan (POP) is structured for a three-year implementation period (2024–2026), aligned with the overall PRO-CLIMATE project timeline. It integrates the four LL phases—Empathise & Define, Ideate & Co-design, Prototype & Pilot, and Test & Evaluate—with key contributions from Work Packages (WPs) as outlined below (Table 7).

Table 7. Implementation Timeline

Year	Phase	Key Activities	Responsible WPs
2024 (Months 1–12)	Phase 1: Empathise & Define	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finalise contextual analysis • Stakeholder mapping • Online and physical workshops kick-off • Co-creation baseline 	WP2 (ATU – Living Lab framework), WP3 (CO-OP – System diagnostics), WP4 (CU – Governance & behavioural insights)
2025 (Months 13–24)	Phase 2 & 3: Ideate & Co-Design Prototype & Pilot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visioning and scenario-building • Development of pilot actions • Implementation of pilot actions • Capacity-building of change agents 	WP2 (Workshops and co-design), WP4 (Behavioural mapping, KPIs), WP5 (UiB – Modelling & stress testing)
2026 (Months 25–36)	Phase 4: Test & Evaluate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact evaluation of pilots • Workshops to supporting living labs in their change processes • Stakeholder reflection loops • Policy recommendations • Preparation of final LL reports and upscaling strategy 	WP4 (Impact evaluation & indicators), WP6 (ULEI – Policy development), WP7 (TERO – Dissemination & exploitation)

This timeline ensures coherence between local interventions and project-wide objectives while embedding flexibility for iterative learning and scaling. Each WP plays a dedicated role in supporting the Living Lab through its operational phases, enabling a systemic and measurable transformation process

6 Conclusion

The Pilot Operational Plan (POP) serves as a pivotal tool within the PRO-CLIMATE project, offering a structured yet flexible roadmap to implement, test, and evaluate climate adaptation strategies across six diverse Living Labs. Grounded in systems thinking and co-creation methodologies, the POP provides the framework necessary to translate the project's theoretical underpinnings into concrete, community-led action.

By progressing through four defined phases—Empathise & Define, Ideate & Co-Design, Prototype & Pilot, and Test & Evaluate—the POP empowers stakeholders to collaboratively address local climate challenges. It fosters inclusive engagement, harnesses behavioural insights, and promotes innovative governance approaches to enable systemic transformation.

The integration of tools and insights from across Work Packages ensures methodological consistency, policy relevance, and scientific robustness. Roles and responsibilities are clearly distributed among Living Lab Leaders, Change Agents, and stakeholders within the Quadruple Helix, reinforcing ownership, accountability, and long-term impact.

Ultimately, the POP is more than a project deliverable—it is a living, evolving mechanism that supports the emergence of climate-resilient communities. It enables local actors not only to respond to the climate crisis but to shape the social and institutional transformations required for sustainable futures across Europe. As the Living Labs move toward the Test & Evaluate phase, the POP will serve as a foundation for policy integration, cross-regional learning, and scalable impact beyond the project's lifecycle.

Annex 1 Badajoz Region Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan

Introduction

The Badajoz Living Lab (LL), developed within the Horizon Europe PRO-CLIMATE project, is rooted in the context of southwestern Spain, a region defined by its rural character, agricultural dependence, and vulnerability to climate extremes. Situated in the province of Badajoz, which is part of the autonomous community of Extremadura, the LL operates within a landscape marked by rising temperatures, extended droughts, and the degradation of vital ecosystems such as the Dehesa.

The region also contends with socioeconomic challenges including rural depopulation, ageing infrastructure, and fragmented governance across local and regional levels. Despite these difficulties, the Diputación de Badajoz offers a strong institutional platform through its network of 14 territorial delegations, which play an important role in supporting place-based responses to climate change.

The Living Lab approach in Badajoz seeks to build upon existing strengths—such as inter-municipal cooperation, a growing interest in sustainable tourism and agri-food innovation, and the mobilisation of research centres like CICYTEX and CTAEX. The LL’s methodology emphasises participatory governance and behavioural transformation, aiming to co-design practical solutions that reflect local knowledge and build long-term resilience. Particular attention is given to empowering women and youth, valorising the Dehesa as a multifunctional climate buffer, and connecting community-led initiatives with institutional planning tools.

This Pilot Operational Plan (POP) outlines the four key phases guiding the LL’s implementation: Empathise & Define, Ideate & Co-Design, Prototype & Pilot, and Test & Evaluate. Each phase is shaped by local realities and informed by transdisciplinary inputs from PRO-CLIMATE’s work packages, particularly in the areas of behavioural diagnostics, co-creation methodologies, and adaptation governance.

Phase 1: Empathise & Define

Contextual Diagnosis

The province of Badajoz, located in southwestern Spain, constitutes a predominantly rural and agrarian territory marked by low-density settlements, extensive agricultural activity, and distinctive ecological landscapes such as the Dehesa. While these features provide cultural and environmental richness, they also expose the region to complex climate-related pressures. Rising temperatures, prolonged droughts, more frequent extreme weather events, and biodiversity loss threaten both natural systems and socio-economic stability. These pressures are compounded by demographic shifts and institutional fragmentation, as outlined in Table 8.

Table 8: Key Contextual Challenges in the Badajoz Living Lab

Category	Key Issues
Environmental Challenges	Rising temperatures and drought stress water supply and agricultural productivity, especially within the Dehesa. Extreme weather contributes to flooding and erosion. Biodiversity loss is accelerating due to shifting climate patterns and changing land uses.
Socio-Demographic Dynamics	Depopulation and ageing communities undermine social cohesion and adaptive capacity. Outmigration of youth leads to reduced innovation potential and land abandonment. Digital exclusion persists in rural areas.
Governance & Institutional	Fragmented governance limits coordination across levels. Weak vertical policy integration and low trust in public institutions hinder participation and policy uptake.

Despite these challenges, the Diputación de Badajoz plays a key role in fostering coordination and supporting municipalities across the province. Through its wide network of administrative

delegations, it provides technical, logistical, and political support to local authorities, creating a valuable entry point for inclusive and place-based adaptation.

The contextual analysis—enriched through participatory workshops involving municipal officials, researchers, and civil society actors—identified multiple opportunities for systemic change. Among these, the Dehesa ecosystem stood out as a cultural and ecological cornerstone. While increasingly threatened by climate impacts and changing land-use patterns, stakeholders recognised its multifunctional value and its potential to serve as a model for climate-smart agroforestry and nature-based solutions.

Participants also underscored the untapped capacity of women and youth in rural innovation. Their limited participation in political, economic, and land-use decisions was seen as a challenge, but also as an opportunity for strengthening inclusive leadership and intergenerational resilience.

Further, several grassroots initiatives around sustainable tourism, circular economy, and regenerative agriculture were presented as viable alternatives to conventional development models. These community-led efforts reflect both a cultural shift and practical avenues for economic diversification and climate adaptation.

Lastly, there was consensus on the importance of aligning local actions with broader policy frameworks—such as the Spanish CSR Plan, ADAPTA LOCAL, and Agenda 2030—to enhance coherence, visibility, and access to funding.

These findings informed the definition of the Badajoz Living Lab's focal action situations and stakeholder engagement strategy. By anchoring pilot actions in locally expressed challenges and capacities, the Living Lab seeks to co-produce adaptation pathways that are both grounded and transformative.

Stakeholder Mapping

The stakeholder mapping in the Badajoz Living Lab (LL) was designed as a foundational element of the Pilot Operational Plan (POP), aligned with the co-creation and engagement principles of the PRO-CLIMATE project. Grounded in a systemic perspective and the Quadruple Helix Model, the process aimed to identify and connect relevant actors across public authorities, research institutions, civil society, and the private sector, ensuring that local adaptation is inclusive, evidence-informed, and context-specific.

Stakeholder Identification and Engagement Approach

Following the integrative methodologies developed under WP2 and WP4, stakeholder mapping was implemented in two iterative phases. The first phase involved desk research based on existing networks, local development strategies, and publicly available institutional data. This allowed for a preliminary mapping of relevant actors based on their formal mandates, operational relevance, and historical involvement in climate and territorial initiatives. The second phase consisted of targeted field engagement—through bilateral meetings, surveys, and participatory sessions held in Mérida and across municipalities coordinated by the Diputación de Badajoz. These interactions helped validate the initial analysis and enrich it with qualitative insights.

Throughout the process, particular attention was paid to identifying not only institutional stakeholders, but also grassroots actors, vulnerable groups, and non-traditional contributors to climate governance. This approach reflects the PRO-CLIMATE commitment to co-creation, knowledge plurality, and local empowerment.

Stakeholder Ecosystem and Functional Roles

The governance landscape of Badajoz is decentralised and layered. At the regional level, institutions such as the Junta de Extremadura and the Oficina Española de Cambio Climático (OECC) provide strategic policy direction and funding instruments. At the provincial level, the Diputación de Badajoz supports coordination, capacity-building, and technical assistance to municipalities. These actors represent the formal backbone of adaptation planning.

On the ground, implementation is led by entities such as the Mancomunidades Integrales (e.g., Olivenza, Guadiana, Sierra Suroeste) and the Federación de Municipios y Provincias de Extremadura (FEMPEX). These bodies ensure local delivery but frequently face challenges related to technical capacity and financial stability—an issue repeatedly raised during workshops.

Knowledge institutions including the Universidad de Extremadura, FUNDECYT-PCTEX, CICYTEX, and CTAEX provide scientific and technical support. They play a central role in risk assessments, innovation testing, and alignment with EU research frameworks.

Civil society stakeholders such as ADEVAG, ADECOM, Fundación Ciudadanía, Plena Inclusión, and Cruz Roja Extremadura are instrumental in supporting inclusion, local awareness, and trust-building. Their involvement ensures that vulnerable and underrepresented groups are part of the adaptation dialogue.

Economic and sectoral actors—including UPA-UCE, APAG Extremadura ASAJA, CREEX, and regional tourism promoters—bring the perspective of agriculture, business, and sustainable development. Their support is key to connecting pilot actions with livelihood needs and long-term economic resilience.

Finally, dissemination and outreach actors such as Ecologistas en Acción and the Red Extremeña de Desarrollo Rural (REDEX) facilitate communication, public awareness, and local ownership—aligning with PRO-CLIMATE's emphasis on behavioural change and civic mobilisation.

Governance and Representation Challenges

During the mapping, several cross-cutting issues were identified, including low institutional trust in rural areas, the limited involvement of youth and women in decision-making, and digital exclusion. These insights confirmed the need for simplified communication strategies, capacity-building measures, and formats adapted to rural realities.

To address these gaps, the Badajoz LL mobilised flexible engagement tools: printed surveys and analogue methods were used to reach digitally excluded communities; co-creation workshops were organised to promote dialogue across sectors; and bilateral meetings enabled tailored discussions with key actors. These approaches are consistent with the inclusive co-design process foreseen under WP2 and WP4.

Role in the POP Lifecycle

Stakeholders identified during the mapping phase are actively involved in shaping, implementing, and monitoring the Badajoz POP. Their inputs inform the focal action situations, pilot interventions, and scaling strategies. This reinforces the Living Lab's role as a platform for distributed ownership, collaborative learning, and long-term resilience building—core principles of the PRO-CLIMATE framework (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Badajoz Living Lab Stakeholder Mapping based on Quadruple Helix Model

Focal Action Situation (FAS)

The Focal Action Situation (FAS) defines the convergence point where climate-related pressures, institutional complexity, and social vulnerabilities intersect, offering a practical and strategic framework for launching integrated adaptation responses. In the Badajoz Living Lab (LL), the FAS has emerged through iterative consultation with stakeholders and reflects a context-specific synthesis of territorial stressors and local capacities.

Territorial and Socio-Ecological Stressors

Badajoz, as part of rural Extremadura, is increasingly exposed to severe climate challenges, including rising temperatures, more frequent and prolonged droughts, biodiversity loss, and growing flood risks. These environmental dynamics are closely tied to social vulnerabilities—most notably, demographic ageing, youth outmigration, digital exclusion, and declining agricultural viability. The Dehesa, an emblematic agro-silvo-pastoral landscape central to the region’s identity and economy, is under increasing pressure from land abandonment, fragmentation, and unsustainable land use.

From an institutional perspective, adaptation planning is hindered by governance fragmentation, limited cross-sectoral coordination, and persistent low levels of trust in public institutions, particularly in rural and peripheral areas. Municipalities often operate with limited capacity and resources, which creates obstacles for implementing coherent, long-term climate strategies and for securing alignment with regional and national policies.

Opportunities for Co-Creation and Adaptation

Through participatory workshops and multi-stakeholder dialogues, several key entry points for transformation have been identified within the FAS. These include:

- **Empowerment of Women and Youth:** These groups remain underrepresented in formal adaptation processes yet demonstrate strong potential as agents of change. Their involvement is essential to fostering new narratives, community participation, and innovation in rural areas.

- **Revitalisation of Water-Smart Agroforestry:** The Dehesa system represents both a challenge and an opportunity. Enhancing its resilience through agroecological practices, improved water efficiency, and nature-based solutions can serve as a model for sustainable rural adaptation.
- **Knowledge Sharing and Local Innovation:** Schools, cooperatives, NGOs, and informal networks can serve as platforms for knowledge exchange, behavioural learning, and community mobilisation. Strengthening these actors can reinforce adaptive capacity at the local level.
- **Policy and Institutional Alignment:** Embedding Living Lab interventions within existing regional frameworks—such as the CSR Plan, ADAPTA LOCAL, and the Agenda 2030 strategy—can help overcome fragmentation and support long-term governance continuity.

The Badajoz FAS is thus structured around a systems-oriented understanding that links local context with adaptive processes. It is articulated across five levels:

- **Inputs:** Locally grounded knowledge, scientific assessments, and insights from stakeholders;
- **Processes:** Co-creation mechanisms, participatory workshops, and engagement strategies;
- **Outputs:** Pilot interventions, engagement tools, and coordination models;
- **Outcomes:** Strengthened trust, enhanced institutional coordination, and behavioural uptake;
- **Impacts:** Improved rural resilience, more inclusive governance, and climate-smart territorial transformation.

Behavioural and Institutional Barriers

The LL recognises that climate adaptation is not only a technical or ecological challenge but also a behavioural and institutional one. Multiple structural and social barriers impede action, including administrative fragmentation, low citizen engagement, and misalignment between actors. The approach adopted in Badajoz addresses these obstacles through four interconnected dimensions:

Stakeholder Co-Creation

Local actors were actively engaged from the beginning through surveys, workshops, and participatory mapping exercises. This continuous involvement ensured that pilot concepts and adaptation priorities reflected both local needs and existing knowledge. Visual facilitation tools and dialogue formats supported inclusive engagement, especially in rural settings.

Institutional Transformation

Progress toward integrated governance was supported by improved horizontal and vertical coordination between provincial and local actors. Although resource constraints persist, efforts were made to align LL activities with broader strategic instruments like the ADAPTA LOCAL initiative, the CSR Plan, and other regionally endorsed development frameworks. Municipal collaboration and multilevel dialogue were prioritised throughout the design phase.

Behavioural Change

Promoting sustainable practices required a shift in habits and perceptions around water use, biodiversity protection, and land stewardship. Behavioural insights from WP3 informed the framing of pilot activities. Educational outreach, analogue communication tools, and targeted awareness campaigns contributed to fostering change, particularly among youth and agricultural stakeholders.

Local Empowerment

To ensure ownership and continuity, the LL invested in community-level engagement through cooperatives, educators, and rural associations. Special attention was given to capacity-building, inclusion of peripheral communities, and the promotion of scalable, low-cost actions that can be sustained beyond the project's duration (Table 9).

Table 9: Key Dimensions for Addressing Barriers in the Badajoz Living Lab

Dimension	Focus	Key Contributions
Co-Creation	Stakeholder-driven design and ownership	Participatory workshops and bilateral consultations ensured alignment with local needs; inclusive tools supported broad community input.
Institutional Transformation	Strengthening governance systems	Coordination with regional plans (e.g., CSR, ADAPTA LOCAL) and local governments enhanced strategic coherence and helped build trust and continuity.
Behavioural Change	Shaping sustainable values and practices	Communication formats and workshops targeted sustainable behaviours related to land use, water, and agroforestry, with attention to local knowledge.
Local Empowerment	Enabling grassroots climate action	Civil society organisations, schools, and community leaders supported bottom-up mobilisation and pilot implementation in rural areas.

By addressing both institutional inertia and behavioural resistance, the Badajoz Living Lab aims to build trust, facilitate knowledge sharing, and support community-led climate action. This layered and participatory approach ensures that adaptation solutions are not only technically sound, but also socially legitimate and territorially anchored.

Phase 2: Ideate & Co-Design

Building on the contextual diagnosis and the comprehensive stakeholder mapping, the Badajoz Living Lab (LL) entered the ideation phase with a clear objective: to co-create actionable and locally rooted adaptation pilots. This phase marked a shift from analytical framing to participatory solution design, and it was shaped by a strong commitment to inclusivity, trust-building, and collaborative ownership.

The co-design process formally began with a two-day in-person workshop held in Mérida in March 2025, which brought together diverse stakeholders representing the Quadruple Helix domains. The event was preceded by several online preparatory sessions, which helped align expectations and introduce the objectives of the Living Lab to key regional actors and facilitators.

Participants in the workshop included delegates from municipal authorities under the coordination of the Diputación de Badajoz, representatives of the Extremadura Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FEMPEX), local development associations, women's cooperatives, ecological groups, NGOs focused on inclusion and disability, regional SMEs from the tourism and energy sectors, as well as research organisations such as CICYTEX and CARTIF. The diverse composition of participants allowed for a rich exchange of knowledge, concerns, and aspirations.

The central goal of the workshop was to collaboratively identify shared priorities and generate early-stage pilot ideas grounded in the local reality. Through interactive group work, stakeholders explored key climate vulnerabilities, mapped resources and knowledge, and envisioned solution pathways. This co-creation process also served as an opportunity to strengthen previously weak links between municipalities, communities, technical experts, and economic actors.

A range of participatory and behaviourally informed methods were used to guide the discussions. Participatory mapping exercises helped visualise how climate change manifests across the province—from drought-affected farmland to depopulating villages. Scenario building sessions prompted participants to reflect on potential futures and the role of adaptation in avoiding risk or unlocking opportunity. Design thinking techniques allowed for reframing problems from the perspectives of local communities and identifying solutions that were both innovative and feasible. Visual boards, note clustering, and open facilitation formats enabled equitable participation, encouraging contributions from voices often marginalised in institutional dialogues.

The process led to the emergence of three interconnected focus areas for pilot action, which are summarised in the table below (Table 10):

Table 10: Focus Areas Identified in the Co-Design Workshop

Focus Area	Specific Pilot Activities
Climate-Smart Agriculture & Agroforestry	Water-efficient practices adapted to arid zones; revitalisation of the Dehesa system through agroecological methods; youth and women involvement in agri-tech; job creation linked to drone-based monitoring and sustainable land management.
Eco-Tourism & Dark-Sky Initiatives	Promotion of low-impact rural tourism; development of thematic trails and dark-sky viewing routes; infrastructure for cycling and nature-based mobility; employment through ecotourism innovation.
Biodiversity & Nature-Based Solutions	Community-led reforestation projects and ecological corridor restoration; vertical gardens and greening in semi-urban areas; drone-based biodiversity monitoring with citizen science components.

These focus areas reflect a balance between stakeholder values, local development needs, and regional ecological priorities. They were selected not only for their feasibility in terms of technical and financial resources but also for their potential to drive behavioural change and institutional learning over time.

The co-design workshop produced several concrete outcomes. First, it built a shared understanding of the LL's strategic objectives, aligning local concerns with the broader vision of the PRO-CLIMATE project. Second, it mobilised a diverse coalition of actors around common goals and created momentum for continued collaboration. Third, it generated early commitments for pilot participation, particularly from municipalities, rural cooperatives, and youth-focused organisations.

The ideas and priorities co-developed in Mérida now serve as the foundation for the prototype and pilot phase. These outputs have been integrated into the POP framework and will be refined in subsequent planning sessions, tested in real-world contexts, and continuously adapted through feedback loops and stakeholder engagement.

As such, this phase marks a pivotal moment in the Living Lab journey—from understanding the problem to collectively imagining solutions, and from fragmented engagement to shared authorship of adaptation pathways.

Phase 3: Prototype & Pilot

The prototyping and piloting phase marks the start of on-the-ground implementation of the co-created adaptation actions in the Badajoz Living Lab. Considering the province's wide territorial spread and rural character, the strategy relies on mobile formats, collaboration with local institutions, and ongoing support from technical partners. Pilots are designed to test context-specific solutions while promoting behavioural change, institutional collaboration, and long-term engagement.

Building on the thematic areas identified during co-design, the pilot actions aim to demonstrate feasibility, social acceptance, and scalability. The implementation is supported by a flexible coordination structure, with Diputación de Badajoz ensuring local access and CARTIF and ATU offering scientific and methodological assistance. Pilots are being tested in selected municipalities, with tools adapted to different levels of digital access, resource availability, and local interest.

Local facilitators such as educators, NGO members, and municipal staff help guide the activities on the ground, encouraging participation and ensuring that learning and feedback are continuously integrated. Capacity-building sessions, practical demonstrations, and community workshops support this process, while evaluation is supported by monitoring indicators defined in connection with WP4.

Below is a summary of the pilot implementation components (Table 11):

Table 11: Pilot Implementation Strategy – Key Components

Component	Description
Pilot Activities	Practical demonstrations on themes such as water-smart agriculture, Dehesa revitalisation, biodiversity corridors, and sustainable tourism routes.
Institutional Collaboration	Local coordination led by Diputación de Badajoz, with technical guidance from CARTIF and ATU. Municipalities and civil society actors are directly involved.
Local Facilitation	Teachers, NGO staff, and local leaders act as facilitators to support implementation, promote engagement, and monitor progress.
Focus Areas	Climate-smart agriculture and agroforestry, sustainable rural tourism, and biodiversity through nature-based solutions.
Policy and Strategic Alignment	Pilot activities align with regional priorities (Agenda 2030 Extremadura, ADAPTA LOCAL), and are designed to contribute to national and EU goals.

This phase allows the Living Lab to move from planning to practice. The outcomes of these pilots will feed directly into the evaluation phase and provide valuable evidence for potential replication across other rural areas in Spain and Europe.

Phase 4: Test & Evaluate

The final phase of the Badajoz Living Lab is dedicated to assessing the effectiveness, inclusivity, and replicability of the pilot actions developed and implemented in earlier stages. This phase ensures that adaptation solutions are not only technically sound, but also context-appropriate and supported by local actors. Evaluation focuses on behavioural change, institutional engagement, and potential for policy integration.

Monitoring activities are carried out using indicators aligned with the PRO-CLIMATE framework and adapted to the specific characteristics of the Badajoz region. Data is collected through both digital and analogue tools to accommodate varying levels of access across rural areas. Local workshops and feedback sessions with project partners support participatory assessment and iterative improvement.

The insights gained from this phase will inform future actions at municipal and regional levels, support knowledge transfer, and strengthen the LL's contribution to broader adaptation policy agendas (Table 12).

Table 12: Monitoring and Scaling Strategy for the Badajoz Living Lab

Category	Key Elements
Monitoring & KPIs	Indicators focus on governance, social inclusion, behavioural change, and alignment with regional strategies (e.g. CSR Plan, ADAPTA LOCAL).
Data Collection	Mix of methods: surveys, observation, local workshops. Tools are adapted to digital and low-tech settings for broad participation.
Effectiveness Indicators	Stakeholder diversity and retention, level of pilot uptake, changes in attitudes or practices, degree of local and institutional engagement.
Risk Management	Anticipated risks include climate variability, political changes, and digital exclusion. Responses include analogue outreach, local anchoring, and flexibility.

Scaling Tools	Development of guides and templates for replication; dissemination through municipal networks (e.g. FEMPEX) and regional coordination platforms.
Policy Uptake	Results will be linked to ongoing initiatives under the Agenda 2030 strategy and regional adaptation frameworks for long-term institutionalisation.

This phase closes the loop of the Living Lab process by translating on-the-ground experimentation into actionable knowledge for policy and practice. Through structured monitoring, inclusive evaluation, and knowledge-sharing, the Badajoz Living Lab reinforces its contribution to sustainable and community-driven climate adaptation.

Conclusion

The Badajoz Living Lab provides a structured and participatory approach to advancing climate adaptation in a rural Mediterranean context. Through a phased process—from context analysis to co-design, piloting, and evaluation—it has brought together public institutions, technical partners, and local communities to address environmental risks and social vulnerabilities in a coordinated and inclusive manner.

The Pilot Operational Plan has demonstrated how climate adaptation can be embedded in local dynamics through practical interventions, targeted capacity-building, and alignment with regional strategies such as the CSR Plan, ADAPTA LOCAL, and Agenda 2030 Extremadura. By fostering collaboration across municipalities, research centres, and civil society actors, the Living Lab has created conditions for local ownership, knowledge exchange, and innovation.

With the transition to the evaluation phase, the Badajoz Living Lab builds on a solid foundation of engagement, institutional support, and applied knowledge. The lessons drawn from pilot implementation will inform future replication and help strengthen rural resilience both within the province and in similar territories across Europe.

This plan contributes directly to the objectives of the PRO-CLIMATE project by translating behavioural and systemic insights into locally meaningful actions. The Badajoz experience offers a practical example of how climate resilience can be developed through grounded, collaborative, and adaptive processes.

Annex 2 Leipzig Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan

Introduction

The Leipzig Living Lab (LL), developed under the Horizon Europe PRO-CLIMATE project, supports the design and testing of inclusive climate adaptation approaches in an urban context shaped by social diversity, institutional complexity, and evolving political dynamics. Rooted in behavioural research and participatory processes, the Pilot Operational Plan (POP) provides a locally tailored framework for addressing climate challenges through collaboration between public authorities, civil society, and knowledge partners.

The LL was initiated at the request of the **City of Leipzig**, with the specific aim of improving the public communication of its climate agenda and enhancing citizen engagement. As such, the process has prioritised direct collaboration with municipal departments, particularly those involved in environmental protection, digital governance, and urban development. Challenges such as fragmented messaging, low citizen uptake of climate programmes, and departmental silos have been central to the diagnosis phase.

Led by the **University of Leipzig**, with methodological support from **Atlantic Technological University (ATU)** and with involvement of **Coventry University (CU)**, the Living Lab complements the city’s existing strategic frameworks, including the **Climate Action Plan (Klimaschutzaktionsplan Leipzig – KLAK)** and the **Integrated Urban Development Concept (INSEK)**. Within this structure, the LL functions as a testing ground for behavioural interventions and participatory governance formats aimed at building trust, improving transparency, and aligning communication across sectors.

Through structured engagement with city officials, NGOs, youth groups, academic experts, and community organisations, the Living Lab focuses on strengthening climate communication, fostering collaborative practices, and identifying opportunities to embed behavioural insights into urban governance.

This POP outlines the vision, methods, and implementation steps of the Leipzig LL across four phases—**Empathise & Define, Ideate & Co-Design, Prototype & Pilot, and Test & Evaluate**—and serves as a guide for advancing Leipzig’s climate adaptation efforts in a way that is socially inclusive, politically grounded, and institutionally actionable.

Phase 1: Empathise & Define

Contextual Diagnosis

The city of Leipzig, located in the federal state of Saxony in eastern Germany, is a major urban centre recognised for its climate ambitions and strong civic participation. At the same time, the city operates within a broader regional context marked by political diversity and socio-economic disparities. These conditions shape both the opportunities and constraints for implementing effective, inclusive climate adaptation strategies.

The Leipzig Living Lab (LL), developed under the Horizon Europe PRO-CLIMATE project, was initiated in close collaboration with the **City of Leipzig**, responding to the administration’s need to improve the communication of its climate agenda and to engage a wider range of citizens in the adaptation process. The Living Lab builds on existing strategic frameworks, including the **Climate Action Plan (KLAK)** and the **Integrated Urban Development Concept (INSEK)**, and is implemented with support from the **University of Leipzig** and Atlantic Technological University (ATU).

The diagnosis phase identified several environmental, social, and institutional challenges that impact the city’s adaptive capacity. These are summarised in Table 13.

Table 13: Key Contextual Challenges in the Leipzig Living Lab

Category	Key Issues
----------	------------

Environmental Challenges	Rising urban heat due to sealed surfaces and limited green space in densely built areas; ecological degradation along urban waterways and green corridors.
Socio-Demographic Factors	Uneven participation across age and social groups; gaps in trust between communities and institutions; limited capacity to mobilise citizens in peripheral areas.
Governance and Coordination	Fragmented interdepartmental coordination; lack of consistent and accessible public messaging on climate topics; varying political priorities across governance levels.

Opportunities for Systemic Change

Despite these challenges, Leipzig offers a favourable setting for piloting integrated adaptation actions. The city benefits from an active civil society, a robust academic sector, and a responsive local administration. The diagnosis highlighted four main areas where systemic progress is feasible:

- **Climate Communication and Public Dialogue:** Developing a coherent and citizen-friendly narrative around climate adaptation, supported by consistent communication across municipal departments.
- **Neighbourhood-Level Engagement:** Strengthening collaboration with local NGOs, youth groups, and community initiatives to address trust deficits and support inclusive participation, particularly in socially polarised districts.
- **Nature-Based Urban Interventions:** Expanding green infrastructure, revitalising river corridors, and enhancing local cooling through decentralised approaches offer visible and actionable entry points.
- **Strategic Policy Alignment:** Linking pilot actions with existing local and regional strategies—such as KLAK and the Saxony Adaptation Strategy—creates synergies for funding, implementation, and long-term integration.

This contextual understanding forms the basis for defining the **Focal Action Situation (FAS)** and the thematic priorities of the Leipzig LL. The insights from this phase guide stakeholder engagement and pilot co-design, ensuring that actions are rooted in local realities while contributing to the broader objectives of the PRO-CLIMATE project.

Stakeholder Mapping

The stakeholder mapping process in the Leipzig Living Lab (LL) was designed to identify, understand, and engage key actors across sectors involved in or affected by urban climate adaptation. Using the Quadruple Helix Model as a guiding framework, the process focused on building a collaborative foundation for co-design, implementation, and long-term institutional learning. Stakeholder mapping was not limited to institutional actors but considered the practical roles, communication gaps, and interdependencies relevant to Leipzig's social and administrative context.

Stakeholder Landscape and Roles

The Leipzig LL operates in a politically diverse environment, where climate engagement varies between municipal departments, community groups, and private sector actors. The central institutional partner is the **City of Leipzig**, particularly through its **Office for Environmental Protection, Sustainable Development Unit**, and departments involved in urban planning and communication. These actors hold formal responsibility for implementing the **Climate Action Plan (KLAK)** and the **Integrated Urban Development Concept (INSEK)**.

Academic input is led by the **University of Leipzig**, supported by expertise from the **Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ)**. These institutions contribute behavioural and

environmental data, scenario planning, and governance analysis. However, their research outputs must be better integrated into public communication and urban policy processes.

Civil society is represented by a network of local organisations and informal initiatives. Groups such as **Ökolöwe**, **Fridays for Future Leipzig**, and neighbourhood associations in districts like Connewitz and Plagwitz contribute to public engagement, especially among youth and politically active communities. These actors have strong mobilisation capacity but often operate outside formal decision-making structures.

The private sector includes organisations with influence in infrastructure, mobility, and building renovation—such as **LWB Leipzig** (municipal housing), **Stadtwerke Leipzig** (public utilities), and members of the **Smart Infrastructure Hub Leipzig**. Their involvement in adaptation depends on stronger alignment with city-led strategies and improved coordination.

Governance Characteristics

Leipzig's governance structure combines formal mechanisms—anchored in municipal planning and policy—with informal and community-driven channels. While the municipality provides a structured platform for strategy implementation, coordination across departments and with external actors remains limited. Informal networks are active in community engagement but have variable access to institutional support or long-term planning processes.

Challenges of Equity and Participation

The mapping exercise revealed important participation gaps. Specific groups—including youth outside formal education, migrant communities, and residents in socio-economically disadvantaged areas—are underrepresented in climate dialogues. Barriers include inconsistent messaging, digital exclusion, and limited transparency in how citizen input is integrated into climate planning.

To improve outreach and representation, the Leipzig LL prioritised:

- Engaging with youth organisations, schools, and student networks;
- Using printed and online tools to increase accessibility;
- Encouraging participation from neighbourhood initiatives and local forums;
- Offering formats adapted to diverse audiences (e.g., community cafés, visual storytelling, mapping exercises).

Mapping Methodology

Stakeholder identification was carried out in two stages. First, a desk-based analysis reviewed relevant actors listed in municipal directories, urban development plans, and previous EU projects. This was followed by field validation through targeted interviews, bilateral consultations, and co-creation workshops, organised by the **University of Leipzig** in partnership with local officials.

Rather than applying rigid typologies, the mapping focused on actual roles in relation to communication, implementation, and behavioural influence. Special attention was given to actors who facilitate trust-building, represent community concerns, or have experience in public engagement on environmental topics (See Figure 5).

Figure 5: Leipzig Living Lab Stakeholder Mapping based on Quadruple Helix Model

Focal Action Situation (FAS)

In the Leipzig Living Lab (LL), the Focal Action Situation (FAS) is framed around one central challenge: the need to improve climate communication within a politically complex urban setting. While environmental risks such as urban heat islands, biodiversity loss, and flooding are present, the core barrier identified through engagement with municipal actors and project partners has been the fragmentation and limited effectiveness of public climate messaging. This communication gap undermines behavioural change, limits civic trust, and delays institutional action.

The Communication Gap as an Entry Point

The LL began with a request from the City of Leipzig to support the development of a more coherent and inclusive communication approach for its climate adaptation agenda. Municipal actors recognised that despite having formal strategies in place—such as the Climate Action Plan (KLAK)—the lack of shared language, accessible tools, and coordinated outreach had led to uneven awareness and limited citizen engagement. This challenge was exacerbated by political polarisation in the broader Saxony region and varying levels of climate literacy among residents.

Through preliminary workshops and bilateral consultations, it became clear that public-facing departments, technical offices, and civil society organisations were often working in parallel, with overlapping but uncoordinated efforts. The need for a shared climate narrative and integrated communication tools became the unifying thread across stakeholder feedback.

Core Areas of Intervention

As a result, the Leipzig LL defined its FAS not primarily through environmental stressors, but through the institutional and social conditions that shape how climate action is understood, supported, and implemented. Key priorities include:

- **Developing a Shared Communication Strategy:** Facilitating the co-design of a common narrative that connects climate risks to everyday urban life, targeting both the general public and internal city departments.
- **Testing Visual and Behavioural Communication Tools:** Exploring the use of framing strategies, icons, signage, and public space interventions to promote simple, consistent messages.
- **Enhancing Internal Coordination:** Supporting the alignment of messaging and outreach across planning, environment, health, and infrastructure units.
- **Engaging Civil Society as Multipliers:** Involving NGOs, local media, and community-based groups to test and disseminate messages in socially and politically diverse districts.
- **Addressing Trust and Accessibility:** Identifying barriers to engagement—such as technical jargon or digital divides—and testing formats that are inclusive and locally resonant.

This FAS places the spotlight on communication as the foundation for behavioural change and institutional integration. The Living Lab’s contribution lies in prototyping, testing, and evaluating climate communication approaches that can strengthen both top-down policy coherence and bottom-up support.

Systemic Framing

The systemic framing of the FAS in Leipzig recognises communication as a bridge across sectors, actors, and priorities. The Living Lab approach integrates the following:

- **Inputs:** Stakeholder interviews, analysis of municipal communication materials, behavioural insights from WP3, and governance reviews from WP4.
- **Processes:** Co-creation workshops with city departments and civil society groups, participatory testing of messaging tools, feedback loops.
- **Outputs:** A prototype city-wide communication concept, visual pilots in selected neighbourhoods, and internal guidance for messaging integration.
- **Outcomes:** Improved public understanding of adaptation goals, greater alignment among city actors, and increased engagement from harder-to-reach groups.
- **Impacts:** A replicable model for climate communication in politically diverse cities, and a foundation for scaling adaptation through shared understanding and trust.

Institutional and Behavioural Barriers

The primary barriers identified are detailed in Table 14, restructured to reflect Leipzig’s communication-focused strategy:

Table 14: Addressing Key Barriers in the Leipzig Living Lab

Dimension	Focus	Key Measures
Communication Coherence	Unifying institutional messaging	Mapping existing materials; co-developing a cross-departmental narrative; piloting shared visuals.
Institutional Coordination	Bridging internal silos	Facilitating joint workshops with city departments; aligning KLAK messaging with implementation tools.
Behavioural Engagement	Making climate action relevant and accessible	Testing language and framing; using physical prompts in public spaces; targeting specific audiences.

Public Trust and Inclusion	Engaging overlooked or sceptical groups	Adapting formats to various levels of literacy; involving local NGOs in testing outreach strategies.
----------------------------	---	--

By placing communication at the centre of adaptation planning, the Leipzig Living Lab addresses a foundational but often overlooked aspect of urban climate resilience. The FAS does not treat communication as an add-on, but as a necessary condition for all other measures—technical, behavioural, or institutional—to succeed. The LL thus supports Leipzig in building a more informed, connected, and responsive climate governance culture.

Phase 2: Ideate & Co-Design

Following Building upon the findings of the contextual diagnosis and stakeholder mapping, the Leipzig Living Lab (LL) initiated its co-design phase with the goal of addressing the city's fragmented climate communication and limited stakeholder coordination. This phase was launched through a two-day participatory workshop held in Leipzig in March 2025, complemented by preparatory meetings with local institutions, NGOs, and research partners. The focus was not on designing technological solutions, but on defining how institutional and civic actors could collectively shape a unified narrative around climate adaptation.

The co-design sessions were requested by the City of Leipzig's climate units and aimed to respond directly to the municipality's need for clearer, more consistent public communication about climate goals and responsibilities. The Living Lab thus focused on bringing together actors from across departments and sectors to formulate shared language, identify engagement barriers, and develop pilot interventions that could bridge the divide between strategy and public understanding.

Rather than producing a fixed set of measures, the workshops served as a platform for dialogue and prototyping. Participants included municipal departments responsible for climate protection, urban planning, digital services, and education, as well as researchers from the University of Leipzig. The key outcome of this process was the collective identification of communication as both a barrier and a leverage point. Fragmented messaging, inconsistent terminology, and institutional silos were seen as hindering public understanding and limiting the impact of existing adaptation strategies. These issues were particularly pressing in socially diverse districts, where trust in municipal communication is often lower.

To guide the development of concrete pilot actions, participants worked collaboratively to define three thematic focus areas, each connected to practical needs and anchored in the municipal context. These are outlined in the revised table below (Table 15).

Table 15. Focus Areas Co-Defined in the Leipzig Living Lab

Focus Area	Pilot Components
1. Integrated Climate Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a unified city-wide message (e.g., "Climate Competence") • Visual and narrative tools for public spaces • Communication formats tailored for diverse audiences (digital/print, visual/audio).
2. Institutional Coordination & Public Dialogue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdepartmental working groups to align communication strategies • Platforms for structured dialogue between city departments, NGOs, and citizen groups • Training for municipal staff on climate communication.
3. Behaviourally Informed Civic Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-designed citizen surveys and local deliberative events • Campaigns targeting social norms and climate literacy • Prototypes for inclusive events in high-priority districts.

These pilot areas were not selected based on technological innovation, but for their potential to trigger institutional learning, improve coherence, and empower local actors. The process confirmed that effective communication is not a supporting element of adaptation—it is a central pillar that enables coordination, trust, and long-term civic engagement.

Outcomes and Transition to Phase 3

The co-design phase in Leipzig marked a shift from fragmented approaches to a shared vision grounded in clarity, accessibility, and civic legitimacy. The process produced:

- A defined need for a unified climate communication strategy, requested and supported by the City of Leipzig;
- Cross-departmental alignment on the importance of transparent, consistent messaging;
- Conceptual frameworks for how public engagement can be diversified and improved through storytelling, framing, and behavioural tools;
- A portfolio of pilots ready to be tested and refined in the next phase, designed to operate at the intersection of communication, governance, and behavioural transformation.

These results are now embedded in Leipzig’s Pilot Operational Plan and form the basis of the Phase 3 prototyping phase. With communication as a unifying thread, the Living Lab is positioned to facilitate better institutional coordination, public participation, and behavioural change, contributing to Leipzig’s broader strategy for socially inclusive, climate-resilient urban governance.

Phase 3: Prototype & Pilot

The **Prototype & Pilot phase** of the Leipzig Living Lab (LL) marks the transition from planning to implementation. Following the participatory co-design process, this phase aims to test a series of targeted pilot actions focused on improving climate communication, fostering behavioural adaptation, and strengthening coordination among municipal actors. These pilots are grounded in Leipzig’s local context and respond directly to institutional requests, particularly the city’s call for better tools to communicate climate goals to citizens and align efforts across departments.

Rather than focusing on large-scale infrastructure, the pilots are designed as modular, low-threshold interventions that combine visual storytelling, participatory signage, and feedback mechanisms. These actions are implemented in close collaboration with the City of Leipzig, the University of Leipzig, and selected civil society partners. Technical and strategic input is provided by the PRO-CLIMATE consortium, ensuring alignment with broader project goals, including those from WP2 (operational planning), WP4 (behavioural indicators), and WP6 (scaling and policy integration).

Each pilot seeks to validate three key parameters: feasibility of implementation within city systems, social acceptance among diverse resident groups, and potential for behavioural or institutional change. Pilots are embedded in real-world municipal and community processes, supported by Leipzig’s existing strategies such as the Climate Action Plan (KLAK) and INSEK 2030 (Table 16).

Table 16. Leipzig Pilot Implementation Components

Section	Title	Key Elements
1	Pilot Rollout Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilots launched progressively from late 2025 into early 2026 • Integrated into Leipzig’s KLAK communication priorities • Use of city branding tools like “Climate Competence” to unify messaging • Mobile information stands and signage in pilot districts • Surveys conducted before and after implementation to capture shifts in perception

2	Institutional Coordination and Technical Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Led jointly by the University of Leipzig and city climate officers • Coordination across departments: urban planning, environmental protection, mobility, and education • Regular briefings to align pilot progress with municipal policy and EU reporting obligations
3	Role of Local Facilitators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selected facilitators from municipal offices, NGOs, and neighbourhood councils • Responsible for hosting pilot events, guiding visitor interaction, and collecting feedback • Serve as intermediaries between institutions and citizens in test districts
4	Focus Areas for Piloting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication & Civic Engagement: participatory signage, co-created slogans, visual storytelling - Heat and Greening: small-scale greening interventions to mitigate urban heat in pilot neighbourhoods - Behavioural Insights: tracking public interaction, monitoring self-reported awareness and motivation
5	Strategic Alignment and Long-Term Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All pilots aligned with Leipzig’s Climate Action Plan (KLAK) and Saxony’s adaptation priorities • Monitoring data contributes to PRO-CLIMATE KPIs on communication effectiveness and behavioural change • Pilots designed for replication in other Leipzig districts and within the wider PRO-CLIMATE network • Outcomes will feed into future rounds of city planning and funding applications

This phase is not intended to produce polished solutions, but rather to create adaptive learning cycles that inform larger institutional shifts. Through visible, participatory formats, the pilots aim to foster climate literacy, increase self-efficacy, and create new channels for dialogue between the municipality and residents. The data collected will support evaluation in the next phase, while also contributing to Leipzig’s broader efforts to build a socially cohesive and climate-ready urban future.

Phase 4: Test & Evaluate

The final phase of the Leipzig Living Lab (LL) centres on assessing the implementation of pilot actions developed during the co-design process. The focus is on understanding whether these pilots—especially those related to climate communication and stakeholder coordination—are effective, inclusive, and scalable. The evaluation framework supports the broader objectives of the PRO-CLIMATE project, emphasising behavioural insight, institutional learning, and alignment with local and European climate policy instruments.

Testing in Leipzig is not limited to outcome measurement but includes the refinement of tools, the gathering of feedback from residents and city actors, and the monitoring of behavioural shifts through ongoing engagement (Table 17). The process is coordinated by the University of Leipzig and the city’s climate adaptation officers, in collaboration with PRO-CLIMATE work packages (WP4 for KPIs and behavioural diagnostics, WP6 for scaling and policy relevance).

Table 17. Evaluation and Scaling Framework for the Leipzig Living Lab

Category	Key Elements
Monitoring and KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation focuses on communication performance, behavioural shifts, stakeholder involvement, and interdepartmental coordination. • Indicators are aligned with PRO-CLIMATE’s WP4 framework and tailored to Leipzig’s context.
Data Collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses both qualitative and quantitative tools: surveys, public forums, participatory feedback sessions, observational methods. • Data is co-analysed by city teams and research partners to ensure relevance and transparency.
Risk Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key risks include fragmented responsibilities, inconsistent messaging, or low citizen engagement. • Mitigation measures involve rapid pilot adjustments (“quick wins”), simplified communication formats, and inclusive facilitation.
Review Mechanism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal workshops held every six months to assess pilot outcomes and update plans. • Results are fed into city learning cycles and governance structures.
Scaling Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a “Climate Communication Toolkit” for citywide application. • Engagement with Leipzig’s KLAK team for mainstreaming successful approaches. • Sharing outcomes through municipal networks and EU platforms.
Long-Term Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutionalising adaptive communication strategies in local planning. • Enhancing Leipzig’s reputation as a city promoting inclusive climate governance. • Contributing to EU missions on climate adaptation and SDGs.

Through this structured evaluation approach, the Leipzig Living Lab aims not only to assess pilot performance but also to consolidate a replicable model of climate adaptation based on effective communication, stakeholder inclusion, and behavioural transformation. By embedding results into city policies such as KLAK and by involving a wide network of actors, the Lab builds the foundations for sustained impact and wider uptake across European urban contexts.

Conclusion

The Leipzig Living Lab (LL) presents a context-specific approach to climate adaptation, designed to improve public communication, foster behavioural insight, and strengthen cross-sector collaboration in a politically nuanced urban environment. Developed within the framework of the PRO-CLIMATE project, this Pilot Operational Plan (POP) outlines a clear and iterative process—moving from contextual diagnosis and stakeholder mapping to co-design, piloting, and evaluation—rooted in Leipzig’s institutional realities and civic landscape.

Throughout the POP, communication has been recognised as both a barrier and a catalyst. The LL was initiated in direct response to calls from municipal authorities for improved public messaging around climate adaptation. Accordingly, pilot actions were not only co-designed with diverse actors but also built around shared narratives and formats accessible to residents, municipal departments, and community organisations alike.

The Living Lab has positioned itself as a collaborative platform where adaptation efforts are shaped through deliberation, tested through public-facing pilots, and monitored using locally adapted

indicators. These efforts are embedded in Leipzig's existing frameworks, including the Climate Action Plan (KLAK) and the Integrated Urban Development Concept (INSEK), ensuring coherence with citywide objectives.

As the Living Lab moves forward into the Test and Evaluate phase, it does so with a strong coalition of actors, a growing base of public support, and tested tools for communication and behavioural engagement. Rather than presenting adaptation as a top-down process, the Leipzig LL demonstrates how inclusive messaging, mutual accountability, and shared ownership can drive institutional coordination and civic participation.

This POP establishes the foundation for continuing experimentation and learning, while offering transferable approaches for other European cities navigating similar social and political dynamics. In doing so, the Leipzig Living Lab contributes directly to the mission of PRO-CLIMATE: advancing equitable, participatory, and locally anchored climate resilience.

Annex 3 Zakynthos Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan

Introduction

The The Zakynthos Living Lab (LL), part of the Horizon Europe PRO-CLIMATE project, serves as a real-world innovation platform for fostering inclusive and participatory climate adaptation on a Mediterranean island where tourism exerts significant pressure on local resources and infrastructure. Through behavioural science, systems thinking, and stakeholder co-creation, this Pilot Operational Plan (POP) outlines a locally embedded strategy to strengthen adaptive capacity and promote sustainable practices.

Zakynthos is increasingly affected by seasonal water shortages, higher temperatures, and the impacts of concentrated tourist activity. These pressures are intensified by institutional fragmentation, gaps in public awareness, and limited civic involvement in climate policy. The LL addresses these challenges by encouraging behavioural change, building local knowledge, and facilitating cooperation among public authorities, civil society, and the tourism sector.

The activities of the Zakynthos LL are developed **with the support of CoopAbility**, which plays a key role in local facilitation, coordination, and stakeholder mobilisation. Technical and methodological guidance is provided by **Atlantic Technological University (ATU)**, in line with the overall structure and objectives of the PRO-CLIMATE project. The LL also benefits from the engagement of municipal bodies, regional authorities, environmental NGOs, academic actors such as the Ionian University, and representatives of the private sector.

Aligned with the **Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plan for the Ionian Islands**, the POP offers a structured but adaptable roadmap for implementing climate actions through the four-phase Living Lab cycle: **Empathise & Define**, **Ideate & Co-Design**, **Prototype & Pilot**, and **Test & Evaluate**. This approach ensures that climate adaptation efforts are locally relevant, community-driven, and positioned to contribute to wider policy objectives across the Mediterranean region.

Phase 1: Empathise & Define

Contextual Diagnosis

Zakynthos, one of the Ionian Islands in western Greece, combines ecological richness with cultural heritage and strong ties to the tourism sector. Known internationally as a summer destination, the island experiences intense seasonal pressures on infrastructure, water resources, and local ecosystems. The socio-economic model is dominated by tourism, which generates employment and income but also creates significant vulnerabilities, especially in the context of climate change.

Key environmental challenges include **seasonal water scarcity**, deteriorating water quality, rising average temperatures, and changes in rainfall patterns, all of which strain local ecosystems and threaten the sustainability of resource use. Some parts of the island's low-lying coastal areas may also be sensitive to **sea-level rise** and flood-related hazards, though these are not uniformly documented across the territory.

At the same time, Zakynthos faces demographic and economic pressures. The **primary and secondary sectors**, particularly agriculture and traditional industries, have been in decline, while overdependence on mass tourism limits economic diversification. Seasonal fluctuation in employment and service demand increases vulnerability and disrupts long-term planning.

Despite these pressures, Zakynthos also presents key opportunities. Community groups and NGOs are active in environmental protection, academic institutions such as the **Ionian University** contribute to scientific understanding and public education, and there is growing momentum for **sustainable tourism initiatives**. The recent establishment of a **local tourism committee** demonstrates political interest in more balanced and climate-resilient development pathways (Table 18).

Table 18. Key Contextual Challenges in the Zakynthos Living Lab

Category	Key Issues
Environmental Pressures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water scarcity and reduced precipitation intensify seasonal stress on water systems. • Rising temperatures challenge biodiversity and public health.
Socio-Economic Dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High dependency on seasonal tourism amplifies economic and ecological vulnerability. • Decline in primary/secondary sectors reduces local resilience.

Opportunities for Systemic Change

The contextual assessment highlights the following priority areas where targeted action can foster climate resilience and behavioural transformation in Zakynthos:

- **Sustainable Water Governance:** Upgrading municipal water infrastructure, encouraging water-saving practices in the tourism sector, and promoting decentralized solutions can improve both efficiency and availability. This includes targeted measures for hotels and seasonal accommodations, which account for a significant portion of summer water use.
- **Tourism Diversification and Heritage Integration:** Expanding eco-tourism, promoting low-impact thematic travel (e.g., agro-tourism, cultural trails), and increasing off-season offerings can ease peak-period pressures and create more stable income streams. Local agricultural products with geographical indications—such as **Zakynthos PGI raisins**, **PDO olive oil**, and **traditional wines**—can be more strongly integrated into the tourism economy.
- **Education and Awareness Raising:** Building public understanding of climate risks and sustainable behaviours across all segments—residents, visitors, tourism businesses, and youth—is essential. This includes campaigns, school programmes, workshops, and collaboration with the hospitality sector.

These leverage points form the foundation of the Zakynthos Living Lab’s strategic approach, guiding stakeholder engagement and the design of pilot actions under the PRO-CLIMATE project.

Stakeholder Mapping

The stakeholder mapping process in the Zakynthos Living Lab (LL) followed a relational and context-specific methodology, designed to support inclusive climate adaptation and improve governance capacity in a tourism-dependent Mediterranean island. In line with the Quadruple Helix model, the mapping identified a diverse spectrum of actors across public administration, academia and research, civil society, and the private sector—each contributing unique knowledge, responsibilities, and influence in shaping the island’s resilience trajectory.

Institutional actors include the Municipality of Zakynthos, the Departments of Environment and Tourism, the Region of the Ionian Islands, the Directorate of Environment and Spatial Planning, the Department of Water Resource Management, the Zakynthos Regional Unit, and DEYAZ (the local water utility). These entities are responsible for local planning, policy implementation, service provision, and coordination with national strategies. The National Marine Park of Zakynthos adds further governance relevance, particularly concerning biodiversity and marine protection.

Academic and technical expertise is provided by the Ionian University, which contributes scientific input on environmental systems, participatory processes, and sustainability education. Atlantic Technological University (ATU) also supports the LL with methodological guidance in line with the broader framework of the PRO-CLIMATE project.

Civil society plays a significant role through organisations such as WWF Greece, Archelon, Yliessa, and Clean Waters Zakynthos. These groups are active in public awareness campaigns, environmental education, and conservation advocacy, serving as intermediaries between institutions and local communities.

The private sector is predominantly represented by tourism enterprises—accommodation providers, travel agents, and leisure operators—alongside local food producers and agricultural cooperatives. Many of these actors are involved in the newly reactivated Local Tourism Committee, reflecting growing interest in sustainability-oriented tourism governance.

Residents, small-scale farmers, seasonal workers, and tourists form part of the broader stakeholder ecosystem. While often excluded from formal decision-making, their experiences and behaviours are crucial to the success of any adaptation strategy.

To promote inclusiveness and transparency, the Zakynthos LL has employed various participatory mechanisms, including stakeholder workshops, community forums, bilateral meetings, and digital communication channels. The initiative also created a visual identity (logo) to increase visibility and foster community ownership of the Living Lab process.

Focal Action Situation (FAS)

The Focal Action Situation (FAS) in Zakynthos represents a strategic convergence point where environmental, socio-economic, and governance challenges intersect—creating both risks and opportunities for advancing systemic climate adaptation. Through co-creation and participatory engagement, the Zakynthos LL frames the FAS as a dynamic space for dialogue, experimentation, and transformation.

Zakynthos, one of Greece's most prominent tourist destinations, is increasingly exposed to environmental pressures including rising temperatures, reduced rainfall, and acute water resource stress—particularly during the peak summer season. These climate impacts are compounded by institutional fragmentation, economic reliance on seasonal tourism, and limited awareness of the long-term implications of unsustainable practices.

However, the island also demonstrates untapped potential for resilience. Community-led initiatives, a growing body of environmental expertise, and increasing stakeholder engagement create fertile ground for innovation. In this context, the Living Lab has identified three interrelated entry points for co-creation:

- 1. Education and Awareness-Raising**

Targeted communication campaigns and training programmes aimed at residents, tourism professionals, and visitors are key to cultivating climate literacy and behavioural change. By fostering understanding and active involvement, the LL supports a cultural shift towards sustainability.

- 2. Sustainable Destination Profiling**

A coherent profile of Zakynthos as an ecologically rich, culturally valuable, and climate-conscious destination can guide strategic planning and policy decisions. Integrating nature-based and cultural tourism into broader economic development supports diversification and long-term stability.

- 3. Social Empathy and Shared Responsibility**

Encouraging a values-based approach to adaptation—rooted in empathy, trust, and collective responsibility—can bridge sectoral divides and enable cooperation between institutions, communities, and businesses.

This FAS is structured through a systemic framing approach, which encompasses:

- **Inputs:** Local knowledge from residents and stakeholders, behavioural insights generated through WP3, and governance diagnostics developed within WP4, supported by academic partners and civil society organisations.
- **Processes:** Co-creation workshops, participatory mapping, stakeholder engagement dialogues, and iterative solution development.

- **Outputs:** Pilot projects addressing sustainable tourism practices, enhanced environmental communication, and locally grounded adaptation actions.
- **Outcomes:** Greater environmental awareness, improved stakeholder coordination, stronger civic trust, and more inclusive decision-making.
- **Impacts:** Institutionalised behavioural change, improved resource governance, and a replicable island-based model of integrated adaptation.

By anchoring the FAS within Zakynthos' distinct ecological and governance realities, the Living Lab operates both as a diagnostic tool and a driver for change. It fosters a transition away from reactive measures and towards forward-looking, participatory strategies for sustainable development—placing communities at the heart of the island's climate resilience journey.

Phase 2: Ideate & Co-Design

Following the contextual diagnosis and stakeholder mapping conducted in Phase 1, the Zakynthos Living Lab (LL) entered its co-design phase with a series of multi-actor meetings and participatory workshops. The process was launched in November 2024 with the first in-person co-creation session and continued through four meetings, the most recent of which took place in May 2025.

These engagements marked a pivotal step in establishing collaborative dialogue among local actors and in initiating the design of climate adaptation interventions tailored to Zakynthos' socio-ecological and economic context.

Objectives and Approach

The co-creation meetings brought together representatives from the Municipality of Zakynthos, regional environmental departments, NGOs, researchers, tourism operators, and community groups. The discussions were structured around the following objectives:

- Establish a shared understanding of climate adaptation priorities, rooted in the specific challenges and assets of the island;
- Identify behavioural bottlenecks and opportunities for collective action;
- Generate early ideas for pilot interventions aligned with the goals of the PRO-CLIMATE project;
- Foster long-term collaboration between public institutions, civil society, and sectoral stakeholders.

The facilitation approach was intentionally flexible and participatory, incorporating open dialogue, storytelling, and visioning techniques to ensure inclusiveness. Key themes included water resource stress, the seasonality of tourism, the fragility of local ecosystems, and the role of education in supporting behavioural change.

Methodological Integration

The co-design phase was supported by analytical frameworks and tools developed under WP3 and WP4 of the PRO-CLIMATE project. These included:

- Behavioural and stakeholder typologies derived from WP3, which were used to assess power asymmetries and identify underrepresented actors;
- Guidance on co-defining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) from WP4, enabling ideas to be connected to measurable outcomes such as community participation, behavioural uptake, and governance responsiveness.

The Zakynthos LL paid particular attention to ensuring that less visible voices—such as small-scale producers, seasonal workers, and community-based NGOs—were integrated into the design process. The sessions also considered feedback from prior bilateral interviews and policy reviews.

Emerging Priorities and Thematic Focus

The co-creation workshops led to the identification of three interlinked areas for pilot interventions, reflecting local priorities and systemic leverage points (see Table 19). These were validated in group discussions and through individual consultations:

Table 19. Pilot Focus Areas Emerging from the Zakynthos LL Co-Design Phase

Focus Area	Pilot Action Streams
Education and Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental literacy campaigns targeting residents, visitors, and tourism professionals - School-based initiatives on local climate risks and sustainable practices - Community exhibitions and workshops promoting behavioural change
Destination Profiling for Sustainable Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of a narrative and branding strategy for Zakynthos as an ecologically sensitive destination - Integration of local gastronomy, agro-heritage, and off-season attractions into tourism offers - Guidelines for tourism businesses to adopt environmentally responsible practices
Cross-Sector Coordination and Social Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthening mechanisms for collaboration between tourism actors, public institutions, and environmental groups - Activities fostering shared responsibility, sense of place, and inclusive decision-making - Participatory events encouraging trust-building and consensus around shared goals

These thematic areas are directly responsive to the island's challenges—particularly the dominance of seasonal tourism, pressure on water resources, and the need for better alignment between economic development and environmental protection. The pilot proposals build upon existing efforts in Zakynthos, including those under the Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plan for the Ionian Islands and the emerging coordination structure around the Local Tourism Committee.

Outcomes and Next Steps

The co-design phase has laid the foundation for a shared roadmap toward climate adaptation in Zakynthos. It has achieved the following:

- **Common Understanding:** The meetings solidified a shared interpretation of the LL's mission, grounded in sustainable tourism and community empowerment;
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** A broad coalition of local authorities, NGOs, businesses, academic representatives, and citizens actively participated;
- **Commitments for Implementation:** Several actors expressed interest in supporting the pilot phase and contributing expertise or in-kind resources.

The outcomes of this phase have shaped the content of Zakynthos' Pilot Operational Plan and prepared the ground for Phase 3: Prototype & Pilot. The LL now moves forward with:

- Finalising partnerships and implementation teams for pilot actions;
- Establishing clear KPIs in line with WP4 guidance, focusing on adaptive governance and behavioural transformation;

- Ensuring continuity and transparency through communication tools and participatory mechanisms.

Through this approach, the Zakynthos LL demonstrates the value of inclusive design processes in shaping adaptive pathways that are locally grounded, socially robust, and strategically aligned with European climate resilience goals.

Phase 3: Prototype & Pilot

The **Prototype & Pilot phase** of the Zakynthos Living Lab (LL) marks the transition from collaborative planning to practical implementation. This stage focuses on translating co-designed adaptation priorities into pilot activities, tested under real-world conditions across the island. As a location shaped by its fragile ecosystems and intensive tourism activity, Zakynthos faces unique pressures. The LL responds by deploying pilot interventions that reflect local challenges and capacities, particularly in the domains of water conservation, sustainable tourism, and circular economy practices.

Building on previous participatory engagements and stakeholder dialogues, the prototype and pilot phase integrates technical knowledge, behavioural insights, and community leadership. It mobilises municipal departments, the tourism and agricultural sectors, environmental authorities, academic institutions, and citizens to implement and assess the selected initiatives. These actions aim not only to test technical feasibility but also to foster institutional collaboration, public trust, and behavioural adaptation.

Pilot activities are being introduced through an iterative, season-sensitive rollout, targeting both the tourism peak and off-peak periods. This sequencing enables pilots to capture different usage patterns, behaviours, and stakeholder responses throughout the year, increasing their relevance and potential for long-term integration (see Table 20).

Table 20. Pilot Implementation Strategy and Operational Components for Zakynthos LL

Section	Title
1. Pilot Rollout Strategy	Deployment of pilot actions during peak and post-tourism season (from summer 2025); Awareness campaigns on water use and environmental stewardship; Promotion of low-impact tourism products and environmental labelling schemes.
2. Institutional Coordination and Support	Coordination supported by the Municipality of Zakynthos and the National Marine Park Authority (NMPZ); Engagement of the Ionian Islands Regional Unit, local tourism committees, and chambers of commerce; Technical support and alignment with WP2 (POP coordination), WP4 (behavioural monitoring), and WP6 (policy dissemination).
3. Role of Change Agents	Local stakeholders, including hospitality providers, farmers, and environmental educators, act as facilitators; Promote good practices (e.g., water conservation in accommodation, sustainable mobility); Monitor reactions, gather user feedback, and support adaptive management.

<p>4. Focus Areas for Piloting</p>	<p>Water Resilience: smart irrigation, water-saving technologies in tourist accommodations;</p> <p>Sustainable Tourism: green trails, eco-labelled businesses, thematic routes focused on cultural and environmental heritage;</p> <p>Circular Economy: small-scale zero-waste initiatives, valorisation of local agri-food products.</p>
<p>5. Strategic Alignment and Impact</p>	<p>Pilots linked with the Ionian Islands’ Regional Development Strategy and relevant local planning instruments;</p> <p>KPIs developed in coordination with WP4, focusing on tourism seasonality, resource efficiency, and local economic sustainability;</p> <p>Outcomes will feed into national and EU-level dialogue on eco-tourism and island resilience.</p>

The pilot phase in Zakynthos aims to build momentum for lasting change by turning abstract strategies into visible, measurable, and participatory actions. Initial activities—such as installing refill water stations, testing nature-based tourism circuits, and engaging hotels in water conservation trials—serve to stimulate dialogue, validate ideas, and create shared ownership among residents, tourists, and institutions.

To support learning and continuous improvement, the pilot implementation is supported by a structured monitoring system and iterative feedback loops. Change agents play a central role in facilitating this process, collecting feedback, and ensuring that interventions remain grounded in community needs and aspirations.

Ultimately, this phase seeks to demonstrate the viability of place-based adaptation strategies, generate a transferable knowledge base, and consolidate institutional and civic commitment to climate resilience. The Zakynthos LL offers a model for how small island destinations can bridge environmental protection with sustainable economic transition—one prototype at a time.

Phase 4: Test & Evaluate

The fourth and final phase of the Zakynthos Living Lab (LL) focuses on evaluating the impact of the pilot actions, with an emphasis on behavioural change, institutional uptake, and the potential for long-term sustainability. As a tourism-dependent island facing increasing environmental pressures, Zakynthos must ensure that the co-created interventions are not only technically feasible but also socially inclusive and capable of being scaled or replicated in similar Mediterranean contexts.

This evaluative phase assesses how well the implemented actions have addressed the island’s climate adaptation and sustainability goals, particularly in areas such as seasonal diversification, water use efficiency, and stakeholder coordination. It further aims to build local capacity, embed learning into municipal structures, and inform wider regional and national strategies on sustainable tourism and island resilience.

The monitoring process is participatory in nature, engaging the same stakeholders involved in co-design and piloting, and ensuring continuity across the Living Lab’s lifecycle. Monitoring indicators and methodologies are tailored to the unique dynamics of tourism and environmental management in Zakynthos, and draw upon the evaluation framework developed under WP6 (see Table 21).

Table 21. Monitoring, Risk Management, and Scaling Strategy for the Zakynthos Living Lab

Category	Key Elements
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p>Monitoring system aligned with WP6 and customised to reflect tourism–climate interlinkages;</p>

	Tracks behavioural change, participation in local governance, tourism diversification, and inclusiveness.
Data Collection & Analysis	Mixed-method approach combining online surveys, interviews, direct observations, and participatory reflection sessions with local authorities and community representatives.
Risk Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key Risks: Fluctuating tourism demand, limited institutional capacity, political or administrative turnover. - Adaptive Measures: Flexible implementation timelines, use of community ambassadors, leveraging of education and tourism networks to maintain continuity.
Review Mechanism	Structured reflection cycles with stakeholders and facilitators; Integration of monitoring insights into future iterations of pilot activities and policy dialogue.
Scaling Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of toolkits and guidelines for transferring successful practices to other Ionian islands and coastal regions. - Collaboration with national tourism and environmental agencies for policy advocacy. - Alignment with European initiatives such as the EU Green Deal and the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy.
Long-term Impact	Contributes to the establishment of a resilient, community-rooted tourism model; Enhances local climate governance and supports the island's transition towards environmentally responsible, year-round tourism.

By embedding evaluation processes within local governance and stakeholder ecosystems, the Zakynthos LL ensures that lessons learned are not lost at the end of the project, but actively shape future strategies and institutional behaviours. The emphasis on participatory monitoring, behavioural indicators, and systemic learning strengthens the LL's legacy as a driver of climate-smart island transformation.

As such, this phase not only measures the results of past actions but also lays the foundation for continued innovation and adaptive governance in the years ahead, ensuring that Zakynthos evolves from a vulnerable tourist destination into a model for sustainable Mediterranean living.

Conclusion

The Zakynthos Living Lab (LL) represents a distinctive initiative within the PRO-CLIMATE project, addressing the specific challenges of a Mediterranean island shaped by seasonal tourism, water scarcity, and ecological sensitivity. By anchoring climate adaptation in participatory governance, sustainable tourism, and behavioural innovation, the LL responds to the dual imperative of protecting natural resources while sustaining local livelihoods.

This Pilot Operational Plan (POP) has provided a structured and locally rooted roadmap for action—beginning with a contextual diagnosis, followed by co-design with stakeholders, prototyping of targeted solutions, and a participatory evaluation process. At its core, the Zakynthos LL places community engagement and institutional learning at the heart of climate resilience, ensuring that adaptation is not imposed, but co-created with those most affected.

Through collaboration with municipal authorities, environmental organisations, tourism actors, and the academic community, the Living Lab has created new spaces for dialogue and experimentation.

The emphasis on themes such as water efficiency, year-round tourism, and inclusive governance reflects a practical understanding of the island's vulnerabilities and opportunities. Importantly, the LL's actions are aligned with existing regional and national strategies—such as the Ionian Islands Sustainable Development Plan—and informed by European frameworks promoting systemic, cross-sectoral transformation.

As the LL moves into the final phase of testing and evaluation, it does so with a broad coalition of engaged stakeholders, a portfolio of locally tailored pilot interventions, and a commitment to long-term learning and institutional integration. This approach increases the likelihood that climate adaptation efforts will endure beyond the project's timeline and be scaled or replicated in other island and tourism-intensive settings.

The Zakynthos LL contributes to the PRO-CLIMATE mission by demonstrating how behavioural change and participatory governance can be harnessed in complex, tourism-dependent territories. It offers a compelling model for climate-smart island development—one that balances economic resilience with environmental stewardship and community well-being.

Annex 4 Gdansk Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan

Introduction

The Gdańsk Living Lab (LL), developed within the Horizon Europe PRO-CLIMATE project, functions as a collaborative platform for urban innovation, aimed at enhancing the city's resilience to intensifying flood risks linked to climate change. Focusing on participatory governance, behavioural adaptation, and systemic change, this Pilot Operational Plan (POP) outlines a strategic pathway for improving Gdańsk's flood management capacity and public engagement in climate adaptation.

Situated on the southern Baltic coast of Poland, Gdańsk has experienced increasingly frequent and severe heavy rainfall events, flash floods, and coastal storms. This vulnerability was exemplified by the severe flooding events of 2001 and 2016—both widely described in local media and public discourse as “floods of the century” due to their scale and impact, which caused widespread damage to infrastructure, housing, and transport. In response, Gdańsk has implemented a series of structural and nature-based interventions, including the development of retention parks and enhanced stormwater infrastructure. However, ongoing challenges such as governance fragmentation, insufficient cross-sector coordination, and low public awareness of flood risks continue to hinder the city's adaptive capacity.

Supported by the University of Gdańsk and in collaboration with municipal agencies, water utilities, and civil society organisations, the Gdańsk LL builds upon existing initiatives while introducing new participatory and behavioural approaches. The LL aims to improve stakeholder cooperation, increase public understanding of climate risk, and support the development of integrated flood resilience strategies.

This POP sets out the Living Lab's approach across four interlinked phases—Empathise & Define, Ideate & Co-Design, Prototype & Pilot, and Test & Evaluate. It integrates methodologies from across the PRO-CLIMATE project, including insights from stakeholder mapping (WP3), behavioural and governance diagnostics (WP4), and policy scaling strategies (WP5 and WP6). Anchored in the realities of Gdańsk's urban development and climate exposure, the LL offers a flexible yet structured framework for fostering systemic adaptation and inclusive decision-making.

Phase 1: Empathise & Define

Contextual Diagnosis

Gdańsk, a coastal city located on Poland's Baltic shoreline, faces a growing convergence of climate-related, infrastructural, and governance challenges. Its geographical position, coupled with rapid urbanisation and increased impermeable land cover, has made it one of the country's most flood-prone urban centres. In recent decades, torrential rainfall and surface runoff have led to repeated urban flash floods—most notably in 2001 and again in 2016, both widely referred to in local media and public discourse as “floods of the century” due to their severity and societal impact (Gdańsk Development Office, 2017; Gazeta Wyborcza, 2016).

This increasing flood risk is further exacerbated by rising sea levels, limited natural retention areas, and a densely built urban fabric that inhibits water infiltration. Despite proactive municipal efforts—such as the development of retention parks and sustainable drainage systems—challenges persist in terms of scaling impact, engaging communities, and bridging the gap between policy ambition and local implementation.

From a socio-economic perspective, Gdańsk has experienced significant demographic and spatial growth. However, this expansion has placed additional stress on drainage and water systems, particularly in newly developed residential areas. While public awareness of climate risks has grown—driven in part by media coverage and civic mobilisation—preparedness levels and behavioural responses remain uneven, and trust in institutional capacity to manage floods varies across communities.

Institutionally, the city stands out nationally for its open governance culture and experimentation with hybrid infrastructure solutions. Local authorities, in collaboration with research institutions such as the University of Gdańsk, have piloted nature-based approaches and integrated planning models. Yet, coordination across sectors remains fragmented, and the long-term sustainability of these efforts depends on greater public participation and the mainstreaming of adaptive behaviours.

Against this backdrop, the Gdańsk Living Lab (LL), under the Horizon Europe PRO-CLIMATE project, aims to foster systemic change by embedding behavioural science and participatory governance into the city's adaptation strategies. The LL serves as a boundary-spanning platform to align scientific knowledge, civic engagement, and institutional learning, ensuring that flood resilience becomes both a technical and social priority (Table 22).

Table 22. Key Contextual Challenges in the Gdańsk Living Lab

Category	Key Issues
Environmental Pressures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing frequency of torrential rain and urban flash floods (notably in 2001 and 2016). - Limited natural retention areas and extensive surface sealing reduce water absorption and elevate flood risk. - Sea-level rise threatens critical infrastructure along the coastline.
Socio-Economic Dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rapid urban development outpaces adaptation measures, especially in newly built districts. - Public awareness is growing, but preparedness and proactive behaviours remain inconsistent. - Citizens express both optimism and scepticism regarding flood management responses.
Governance & Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong municipal leadership in combining engineering and nature-based approaches. - Collaboration with the University of Gdańsk and other partners provides technical capacity, but coordination can be improved. - Key governance gaps persist in engaging citizens, scaling initiatives, and aligning across departments.

Opportunities for Systemic Change

The Gdańsk LL identifies several strategic areas where targeted interventions could accelerate urban flood resilience and support systemic adaptation:

1. **Integrated Flood Management through Hybrid Infrastructure**
Building on the city's investment in retention parks and green-blue corridors, the LL supports the expansion of multifunctional infrastructure. Combining grey engineering with nature-based solutions can reduce runoff, enhance microclimates, and serve both ecological and recreational functions.
2. **Civic Literacy and Behavioural Preparedness**
Engaging schools, residents, and neighbourhood associations through tailored awareness campaigns, educational tools, and flood preparedness programmes can promote behavioural change. Citizen involvement in monitoring and maintaining adaptation measures also strengthens accountability.
3. **Collaborative Governance Models**
Gdańsk offers a favourable environment for piloting governance innovation. Initiatives such as participatory budgeting for adaptation projects or the formation of cross-sectoral climate task forces could serve to integrate local knowledge into planning and enhance institutional transparency.
4. **Policy Integration and Knowledge Transfer**

Ensuring alignment with national adaptation plans and EU priorities (such as the European Climate Adaptation Strategy and Green Deal objectives) provides a pathway for scaling successful pilots. Capturing and transferring lessons learned across Polish and Baltic coastal cities enhances replicability.

Through this diagnostic lens, the Gdańsk LL positions itself as a strategic actor in enabling participatory, evidence-informed, and behaviourally aware adaptation. By building upon existing city strategies while actively addressing identified gaps, it seeks to foster a resilient, inclusive, and climate-ready urban environment.

Stakeholder Mapping

The stakeholder mapping process in the Gdańsk Living Lab (LL) was designed to reflect the city’s complex governance and environmental context, with a specific focus on flood resilience and climate adaptation. Using the Quadruple Helix model, the process identified key actors from public institutions, academia, civil society, and the private sector (Figure 6). The mapping exercise builds upon existing initiatives in water management, nature-based solutions, and participatory governance already active within the city.

Figure 6. Gdańsk Living Lab Stakeholder Mapping based on Quadruple Helix Model

Identified Stakeholders and Their Roles

The core institutional actors include the City of Gdańsk, particularly the Department of Ecology and Climate, and Gdańsk Water (GIWK), which oversees stormwater infrastructure. These bodies are responsible for the implementation of both grey and green infrastructure solutions. Additional public authorities such as State Water Holding “Polish Waters” and the Regional Directorate for Environmental Protection are involved in regulatory oversight and environmental planning.

Academic input is provided by the University of Gdańsk, which offers expertise in coastal dynamics, urban hydrology, and climate science. These research contributions support the design of evidence-based adaptation measures and evaluation methods.

Civil society plays a growing role in public engagement and awareness. Local organisations, including Tricity Without Smog and community-based initiatives, contribute to education campaigns and the mobilisation of residents, particularly in districts frequently affected by flash floods. Although

participation by vulnerable groups has been limited in the past, recent efforts focus on creating more accessible entry points for dialogue and feedback.

Private stakeholders include real estate developers, infrastructure contractors, and utility service providers. While they are not direct participants in public planning, their actions significantly influence land use and surface permeability, making their engagement essential for sustainable urban drainage strategies.

Methodology

The stakeholder mapping combined desk-based policy review with bilateral meetings and targeted interviews. Functional typologies were used to classify actors as decision-makers, implementers, experts, affected populations, or supporters. Special attention was given to identifying underrepresented voices, particularly among communities most exposed to flood risks.

Governance Structures and Interactions

Gdańsk's urban governance benefits from a high level of institutional capacity and previous investment in hybrid infrastructure. However, coordination across departments and levels of governance remains a challenge, especially where responsibilities for stormwater, spatial planning, and environmental protection intersect. The LL seeks to act as a neutral facilitator by strengthening links among institutions and encouraging co-responsibility in adaptation planning.

Engagement Mechanisms

The Gdańsk LL promotes inclusive participation through structured co-creation events, participatory mapping, and public consultations. These are supported by simplified communication tools and efforts to reach digitally excluded or socially vulnerable groups. Specific focus has been placed on involving residents in low-lying areas, neighbourhood councils, and schools to broaden awareness and build local ownership.

The outputs of the stakeholder mapping have informed the design of pilot activities, ensuring that adaptation strategies are not only technically feasible but also grounded in the realities and capacities of the city's diverse communities.

Focal Action Situation (FAS)

The Focal Action Situation (FAS) in the Gdańsk Living Lab focuses on the city's growing vulnerability to urban flash floods caused by increasingly intense rainfall events. Located along the Baltic coast, Gdańsk has experienced multiple extreme flood episodes over the past two decades—particularly in 2001 and 2016—causing damage to infrastructure and posing serious risks to public safety. Between 2010 and 2017 alone, over 500 significant rainfall events were recorded, underscoring the urgency of more coordinated and inclusive adaptation responses.

These risks are amplified by factors such as sealed surfaces, ageing drainage systems, and dense urban expansion. At the same time, fragmented governance and limited citizen involvement further reduce the city's capacity to respond effectively. Within this context, the Gdańsk Living Lab prioritises flood resilience as its main intervention area, aiming to transition from reactive responses to proactive, system-wide solutions.

Entry Points for Co-Creation

Stakeholder consultations and technical analyses have helped identify several opportunities for collaborative adaptation in Gdańsk. First, the expansion of nature-based and hybrid flood mitigation solutions—such as green retention areas, rain gardens, and permeable surfaces—offers a practical alternative to conventional engineering infrastructure. These initiatives benefit from earlier local pilots and are supported by research partners like the University of Gdańsk.

Second, engaging residents, local associations, and schools in educational and awareness-building activities contributes to improved understanding of water risks and greater public support for adaptation measures. Communication tools and participatory formats aim to simplify complex information and empower communities to take part in shaping their own resilience strategies.

Institutional coordination also emerged as a key challenge and opportunity. Strengthening cooperation between municipal departments, Gdańsk Water, and civil society organisations can enhance planning and implementation processes. The LL seeks to provide a neutral platform to support these interactions, while also piloting new mechanisms for feedback, transparency, and learning.

Systemic Framing of the FAS

The Gdańsk FAS is built on inputs from technical assessments, community engagement, and governance reviews. The process combined co-creation workshops, interviews, and stakeholder meetings to define a common understanding of the city's main climate stressors and adaptation needs. As a result, the LL focuses on:

- **Inputs:** Scientific knowledge from the University of Gdańsk, community insights gathered during co-creation activities, and frameworks from WP3 (behavioural analysis) and WP4 (governance and KPIs).
- **Processes:** Joint visioning, scenario-building, and local diagnostics related to water management and public engagement.
- **Outputs:** Pilot actions aimed at improving retention capacity, flood risk communication, and local collaboration models.
- **Outcomes:** Improved institutional coordination, expanded nature-based infrastructure, and increased community participation.
- **Impacts:** Strengthened adaptive capacity, behavioural shifts around water use and urban resilience, and a transferable model for other flood-prone cities.

By grounding the LL's actions in real-world risks and local collaboration, the Gdańsk FAS supports a structured transition toward long-term urban climate resilience.

Behavioural and Institutional Barriers

The adaptation landscape in Gdańsk is shaped by a mix of infrastructural limitations, low public engagement, and institutional fragmentation. These barriers hinder the uptake of innovative flood resilience solutions and prevent the alignment of policy goals with citizen expectations. The Living Lab tackles these challenges through four interrelated dimensions (Table 23), aligning with the broader framework of the PRO-CLIMATE project.

Table 23. Key Dimensions for Addressing Barriers in the Gdańsk Living Lab

Dimension	Focus	Key Contributions
Co-Creation	Participatory flood adaptation	Stakeholder mapping, bilateral interviews, and collaborative workshops involving municipal services, technical experts, and local communities.
Institutional Transformation	Integrated governance for water resilience	Improved coordination between the City of Gdańsk, GIWK (Gdańsk Water), and regional authorities; alignment of infrastructure planning with adaptation.
Behavioural Change	Water-conscious urban practices	Awareness campaigns, school programmes, and citizen science initiatives to promote risk understanding and shared responsibility.
Local Empowerment	Strengthening community ownership	Involvement of residents in flood monitoring, local mapping, and participatory evaluation of green infrastructure effectiveness.

These interventions help build a foundation of trust, increase the legitimacy of flood risk governance, and support the city's ambition to become a resilient, inclusive, and well-prepared urban environment in the face of accelerating climate impacts.

Phase 2: Ideate & Co-Design

Following the contextual analysis and stakeholder mapping undertaken in Phase 1, the Gdańsk Living Lab entered its co-design phase with a clear focus: the development of inclusive and adaptive responses to the city’s intensifying urban flash flood risks. Given Gdańsk’s exposure to increasingly frequent torrential rains, the co-design phase aimed to move from shared understanding to jointly developed pilot solutions grounded in local realities.

This phase was launched with an in-person workshop in April 2024, hosted by the University of Gdańsk and attended by a broad coalition of stakeholders. Participants included representatives from the municipal government, public utility companies, water management agencies, civil society organisations, researchers, and citizens. The event built on earlier bilateral meetings and consultations and provided a collaborative space to reflect on existing flood mitigation efforts, assess behavioural and institutional barriers, and co-develop priorities for Living Lab interventions.

The workshop combined scenario-building exercises, participatory mapping, and guided discussions to encourage cross-sectoral exchange. Emphasis was placed on ensuring balanced participation, particularly from youth groups, neighbourhood associations, and civic organisations often excluded from formal planning processes. These efforts were informed by guidance from WP3 (stakeholder typologies and behavioural levers) and supported by WP4 in identifying measurable outcomes for Living Lab pilots.

Key Insights and Emerging Priorities

Several important insights emerged from this co-design process. Participants acknowledged the need to strengthen the city’s dual-track approach to flood risk—combining engineered solutions such as stormwater retention infrastructure with nature-based measures like green corridors and rain gardens. A lack of consistent communication and limited opportunities for citizen engagement were highlighted as major obstacles to more inclusive climate resilience planning.

Stakeholders also noted that while technical expertise in the city is strong, more effective collaboration between municipal departments, research institutions, and residents is required. These findings laid the groundwork for the definition of key focus areas for piloting.

Pilot Focus Areas

The co-creation process culminated in the identification of three main focus areas for the development of pilot actions (Table 24). These areas reflect both the urgency of Gdańsk’s climate risks and the capacity of local actors to co-develop and test solutions through the Living Lab.

Table 24. Focus Areas Emerging from the Co-Design Process

Focus Area	Pilot Activities
Urban Flood Resilience through Nature-Based Solutions	Restoration and extension of green spaces and rain gardens; implementation of bioswales and permeable surfaces in target districts; co-maintenance initiatives involving schools and residents.
Climate Communication and Civic Awareness	Co-designed campaigns on flood preparedness; local workshops; development of communication tools such as early alert apps and public information platforms.
Cross-Sector Governance for Flood Risk Management	Establishment of a municipal coordination platform involving key actors; participatory planning tools; testing of decision-making simulations to improve transparency and alignment.

These pilot concepts were selected for their relevance to Gdańsk’s ongoing efforts in stormwater management, and their potential to scale within and beyond the city. Each is intended to foster stronger civic engagement, more integrated governance, and behavioural change aligned with the city’s resilience goals.

Outcomes and Next Steps

The co-design phase marked a turning point in the Living Lab process. Key achievements include:

- A shared prioritisation of urban flash flooding as the central environmental challenge for Gdańsk;
- A common understanding of the need to blend technical and community-based approaches;
- Identification of communication and trust gaps between institutions and the public, and a commitment to address them through Living Lab interventions;
- Expression of interest from municipal agencies, academic institutions, and civil society to support the upcoming piloting phase.

The Gdańsk LL will now transition to the Prototype & Pilot phase with three immediate priorities:

- Clarifying stakeholder roles and responsibilities for pilot implementation;
- Defining KPIs in coordination with WP4 (D4.2) focused on behavioural impact, cross-sector collaboration, and social equity;
- Ensuring continued integration of insights from WP3 and WP4 to guide intervention design and adaptive monitoring.

Through this collaborative and iterative process, the Gdańsk Living Lab is positioned to transform co-created concepts into practical, context-specific actions that support flood resilience and systemic change.

Phase 3: Prototype & Pilot

The Prototype & Pilot phase marks the transition from co-design to implementation within the Gdańsk Living Lab (LL). Building on previous assessments, stakeholder mapping, and participatory workshops, this stage initiates the testing of locally grounded solutions that respond to Gdańsk's most critical climate risk—urban flash floods caused by increasingly intense and frequent rainfall events.

The selected pilot interventions aim to demonstrate how behavioural adaptation, nature-based solutions (NBS), and improved governance mechanisms can collectively enhance the city's resilience. Actions are tailored to specific neighbourhoods within the administrative boundaries of Gdańsk, with emphasis on areas known to be vulnerable to flash flooding.

Pilot Objectives and Priorities

The primary aim of the pilot phase is to validate small-scale, actionable interventions that can reduce flood risk, improve public preparedness, and strengthen institutional coordination. The focus is threefold:

- **Urban Flood Resilience:** Use of nature-based interventions—such as rain gardens, bioswales, and permeable pavements—to enhance stormwater absorption and retention.
- **Civic Awareness and Behavioural Change:** Development of educational activities and public campaigns to raise awareness of urban water risks and promote individual and community responsibility.
- **Governance Innovation and Feedback:** Creation of data-driven feedback loops and coordination platforms that support evidence-based decision-making and participatory planning.

Stakeholder Engagement and Roles

The pilot implementation draws upon existing collaborations established in earlier phases. Responsibilities are distributed across several key actor groups:

- **Municipal Authorities:** The City of Gdańsk, supported by its Urban Green and Blue Infrastructure teams, leads the implementation of green infrastructure pilots and supports coordination with other public institutions.
- **Academic Partners:** The University of Gdańsk contributes technical expertise, provides hydrological monitoring tools, and assists in evaluating pilot impacts.
- **Local Communities and Civil Society Organisations:** Engage in co-assessment activities and help ensure that pilots respond to lived realities in flood-prone districts.
- **Change Agents:** Trained facilitators embedded in neighbourhood structures support behavioural nudges, mediate between citizens and institutions, and collect qualitative feedback.

Focus Areas for Piloting

The Gdańsk LL has structured its pilot phase around three thematic clusters (Table 25), which were refined through stakeholder consultations and aligned with WP2, WP3, and WP4 of the PRO-CLIMATE project.

Table 25. Focus Areas and Pilot Actions in the Gdańsk Living Lab

Cluster	Focus	Pilot Actions
1. Urban Flood Resilience	Adaptation to heavy rainfall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Installation of rain gardens and bioswales in targeted locations - Community-led rainwater harvesting projects - NBS demonstration projects in schools
2. Behavioural Awareness & Communication	Enhancing citizen knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flood risk awareness campaigns (digital and offline) - Participatory mapping of flood-prone zones - “Flood Walks” guided by trained local agents
3. Governance and Monitoring	Data-driven decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of public dashboards to visualise rainfall and impact data - Feedback mechanisms linked to city planning - KPI tracking of behavioural and institutional outcomes

Strategic and Policy Alignment

The pilot activities are embedded within Gdańsk’s ongoing Blue-Green Infrastructure Plan and the city’s broader climate adaptation agenda. They also support national objectives under Poland’s Urban Policy and Climate Policy, and are aligned with EU goals under the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change and the Green Deal.

This phase not only aims to test the technical feasibility of targeted solutions but also to validate their social acceptability and governance fit. It establishes a collaborative model of adaptive experimentation, reinforcing local ownership while generating policy-relevant insights for future upscaling.

Insights from the pilot activities will inform refinements to the Living Lab’s implementation strategy. The evidence generated will also support the upcoming Test & Evaluate phase, where impact assessment, risk analysis, and potential replication pathways will be further explored. Through this

phase, Gdańsk aspires to become a leading example of participatory urban climate resilience in the Baltic region.

Phase 4: Test & Evaluate

The Test & Evaluate phase of the Gdańsk Living Lab (LL) serves as the final step in the pilot cycle, focusing on validating the relevance, feasibility, and impact of co-designed interventions targeting urban flash flooding. These activities build on the work initiated in earlier phases, with a strong emphasis on nature-based solutions (NBS), behavioural change, and collaborative governance.

This phase ensures that the interventions tested during piloting are not only technically sound, but also socially accepted and institutionally viable. The approach combines evidence-based monitoring with continuous feedback from stakeholders, enabling adaptive learning and preparing the ground for longer-term integration into Gdańsk's climate and water management strategies.

Monitoring and Evaluation Approach

Evaluation activities are grounded in the monitoring framework developed through WP6 of the PRO-CLIMATE project, while KPIs have been adapted to the local context with support from WP4. These indicators assess progress in several key domains: community engagement, NBS uptake, institutional transparency, and behavioural shifts related to flood preparedness.

A mixed-methods approach to data collection is applied, including direct observation of pilot zones, drone-based imagery, citizen feedback gathered through workshops and surveys, and interviews with local officials and implementing partners. These insights are used to evaluate both the effectiveness and the inclusiveness of the Living Lab's actions (Table 26).

Table 26. Monitoring, Risk Management, and Scaling Strategy for the Gdańsk LL

Category	Key Elements
Monitoring & KPIs	Indicators assess the adoption of NBS, public awareness, stakeholder collaboration, and inclusiveness in flood risk governance.
Data Collection	Combination of field monitoring, drone imaging, resident feedback, municipal interviews, and participatory evaluation led by the University of Gdańsk.
Risk Management	Risks include infrastructure overload, institutional inertia, and low public trust. Mitigations involve flexible planning, stakeholder dialogue, and early media engagement.
Review Mechanism	Quarterly learning sessions with stakeholders and project teams to evaluate progress, refine actions, and support knowledge transfer.
Scaling and Policy Integration	Development of practical guidelines for NBS replication in other Polish cities; promotion via city networks and EU partnerships; integration with national water and climate policies.

Outcomes and Long-Term Impact

This phase is designed to turn short-term experimentation into long-term transformation. By embedding nature-based and participatory approaches into Gdańsk's existing strategies—such as its Blue-Green Infrastructure Plan and local adaptation policies—the Living Lab supports institutional learning and systemic change.

The review and refinement mechanisms enable both technical optimisation of the pilot actions and stronger social legitimacy, helping to bridge the gap between policy ambition and local implementation. The success of this phase is measured not only by reduced flood risks but also by greater collaboration across municipal departments, citizen involvement, and shared accountability.

Through its structured yet flexible evaluation framework, the Gdańsk Living Lab contributes to a broader European agenda on urban resilience. It provides actionable knowledge for replication in other cities facing similar climate pressures and positions Gdańsk as a frontrunner in citizen-engaged flood adaptation.

Conclusion

The Gdańsk Living Lab (LL) represents a structured and collaborative effort to strengthen urban climate resilience in response to the city's increasing exposure to torrential rainfall and flash flooding. Rooted in the PRO-CLIMATE project's emphasis on systemic transformation and behavioural change, the LL has developed an integrated approach that combines scientific expertise, municipal leadership, and citizen participation.

This Pilot Operational Plan (POP) provides a clear roadmap for climate adaptation—from contextual analysis and stakeholder engagement to co-design, piloting, and performance evaluation. The LL has mobilised a diverse network of local actors, including municipal authorities, universities, civil society organisations, and technical agencies, to co-create and test practical solutions such as nature-based retention systems, flood risk communication strategies, and shared governance platforms.

Building on Gdańsk's prior investments in infrastructure and water management, the Living Lab contributes to a shift from reactive responses to a forward-looking adaptation model that is inclusive, evidence-based, and locally grounded. Pilot activities focus on reducing the physical impacts of urban flooding while strengthening institutional coordination and increasing public awareness.

As the Gdańsk LL progresses through the Test and Evaluate phase, it benefits from established partnerships and early pilot outcomes that offer valuable insights into what works on the ground. The project's emphasis on learning, dialogue, and transparency ensures that pilot interventions remain relevant and adaptable, both within the city and beyond.

By positioning Gdańsk as a leading example of citizen-engaged climate adaptation in Poland, the Living Lab contributes not only to local resilience but also to broader European knowledge on urban flood governance. Its experience offers a transferable framework for other coastal and flood-prone cities working to build inclusive and durable responses to climate risks.

Annex 5 Sligo Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan

Introduction

The Sligo Living Lab (LL), developed under the Horizon Europe PRO-CLIMATE project and building upon the work initiated through the H2020 SCORE project, functions as a real-world platform for climate adaptation in a vulnerable coastal region of Ireland. It brings together scientific tools, participatory methods, and behavioural approaches to co-create responses to mounting climate risks affecting both urban and rural communities in County Sligo.

Situated on Ireland’s Atlantic seaboard, Sligo is increasingly affected by sea-level rise, pluvial and coastal flooding, storm surges, and the erosion of sensitive coastal zones. These environmental challenges are compounded by infrastructural ageing, spatial planning constraints, and limited public engagement with climate adaptation. The Living Lab addresses these issues by integrating low-cost environmental sensors, digital twin modelling, and structured community participation, ensuring that interventions are evidence-based and context-sensitive.

The Sligo LL is supported by Atlantic Technological University (ATU), in close collaboration with Sligo County Council. It operates through a multi-actor framework grounded in the Quadruple Helix Model, engaging local authorities, researchers, civil society, private sector actors, and communities—including youth and residents of high-risk areas. The LL fosters collaboration across technical, institutional, and social domains to shape inclusive and adaptive responses.

This Pilot Operational Plan (POP) provides a strategic framework to guide the Sligo LL through the four key phases of the Living Lab process: *Empathise & Define*, *Ideate & Co-Design*, *Prototype & Pilot*, and *Test & Evaluate*. It is informed by local flood modelling, vulnerability assessments, and the outputs of participatory workshops held with stakeholders across the region. The plan outlines how adaptation actions will be implemented, monitored, and evaluated using tailored Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), with an eye towards replication and integration into local and national strategies.

In contributing to the PRO-CLIMATE mission, the Sligo Living Lab offers a scalable model for data-informed, community-driven adaptation in coastal settings—anchored in collaboration, digital innovation, and behavioural insight.

Phase 1: Empathise & Define

Contextual Diagnosis

The Sligo Living Lab (LL), situated in the northwest of Ireland, operates within a coastal and rural landscape characterised by ecological richness, dispersed communities, and growing vulnerability to climate-related hazards. The region faces significant environmental pressures, including rising sea levels, coastal erosion, and more frequent extreme weather events, posing risks to both ecosystems and local livelihoods. In response, the Sligo LL works to co-develop locally embedded adaptation strategies, grounded in ecosystem-based approaches, citizen science, and digital innovation (Table 27).

Table 27. Key Contextual Challenges in the Sligo Living Lab

Category	Key Issues
Environmental Pressures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Sea-level rise and storm surges increasingly affect low-lying areas such as Strandhill and Easkey. – More frequent flooding, erosion, and landslides linked to climate variability. – Degradation of coastal dune systems and wetlands, threatening biodiversity.
Socio-Economic Dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Regional dependence on agriculture and tourism leaves the local economy exposed to climate shocks.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Rural dispersion and ageing population make sustained engagement more complex. – Limited technical capacity constrains long-term climate planning at community level.
Governance Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Fragmented institutional responsibilities and lack of specific adaptation mandates at county level. – Need for stronger coordination between Sligo County Council, environmental agencies, and local actors. – Gaps in mainstreaming adaptation across sectors and planning frameworks.

Despite these challenges, Sligo possesses notable assets that support resilience-building. Environmental NGOs, community groups, and academic institutions—including Atlantic Technological University (ATU) Sligo—have actively contributed to coastal restoration, local monitoring initiatives, and participatory research. The Smart EARTH Innovation Hub and the Digital Twin initiative provide a strong foundation for using low-cost sensor networks and real-time data in local decision-making. These innovations, coupled with established relationships with Sligo County Council and national bodies such as the OPW and Geological Survey Ireland, create an enabling environment for adaptive action.

This diagnostic phase, informed by stakeholder interviews, workshops, and document review, has highlighted priority action areas such as flood management, coastal protection, and the integration of ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA) practices. These findings will guide the co-design of the Sligo LL’s pilot interventions.

Opportunities for Systemic Change

The contextual analysis points to four key leverage points for enabling systemic change in the Sligo Living Lab:

- 1. Community-Led Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA):** The LL builds on grassroots experience in dune restoration, afforestation, and local monitoring. Formalising these efforts within governance structures, supported by targeted funding, can scale their impact and serve as models for replication in other coastal regions.
- 2. Participatory Governance and Multi-Actor Collaboration:** Co-led by Sligo County Council and ATU, the LL facilitates collaboration between public authorities, researchers, and community stakeholders. Strengthening this platform and broadening participation—particularly from farmers, fishers, and younger residents—can improve trust, representation, and decision-making quality.
- 3. Smart Monitoring and Data-Driven Planning:** The use of sensor technology and data visualisation tools (such as the Digital Twin) enables evidence-based responses to coastal erosion, flooding, and biodiversity threats. Expanding these tools in cooperation with agencies like OPW and the Geological Survey of Ireland will improve the precision and relevance of local adaptation strategies.
- 4. Policy Integration and Sustainable Resourcing:** Aligning LL interventions with national policies such as the Climate Action Plan, and accessing resources via CARO and regional planning mechanisms, supports long-term continuity. Embedding the Living Lab model within county-level planning documents will help mainstream adaptation efforts and institutionalise nature-based solutions.

Together, these opportunities position the Sligo LL as a place-based mechanism for testing and refining systemic climate adaptation approaches, rooted in both scientific evidence and community knowledge.

Stakeholder Mapping

The Sligo Living Lab (LL) adopts a systems-based stakeholder mapping approach rooted in the Quadruple Helix model. This ensures the inclusion of key actors from public authorities, academia, civil society, and the private sector, reflecting the region's socio-ecological complexity and the collaborative ethos of the LL. The mapping has been shaped through a combination of desk research, bilateral interviews, and participatory workshops held between 2023 and 2024.

Identified Stakeholders and Their Roles

The stakeholder landscape in Sligo is characterised by a combination of formal institutions responsible for climate governance and a wide array of informal actors whose local knowledge and place-based experience are vital to the success of adaptation efforts.

Sligo County Council holds the principal coordinating role, overseeing local climate action and working closely with national entities such as the Office of Public Works (OPW), the National Parks and Wildlife Service (NPWS), the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), and the Climate Action Regional Office (CARO). These institutions provide policy direction, regulatory oversight, and access to technical expertise and funding.

Academic partners, particularly Atlantic Technological University (ATU) and associated research institutes, support data collection, environmental monitoring, and the use of smart tools, such as sensor networks and digital twins. Their collaboration with local government enhances knowledge exchange and informs decision-making.

Civil society is represented by environmental groups such as Clean Coasts, local volunteer associations, and place-based initiatives. These actors facilitate outreach, raise awareness, and ensure grassroots concerns are channelled into formal planning processes. Their role has proven essential in maintaining trust and ensuring that communication strategies remain accessible and inclusive.

Landowners, residents, farming communities (including the Irish Farmers' Association – IFA), and coastal tourism operators are among the directly affected stakeholders. They are central to both the co-design and implementation of adaptation measures, particularly those concerning land use, resource management, and public safety in the face of coastal hazards.

Governance Structures and Interdependencies

The Sligo LL operates within a hybrid governance model. Formal channels, led by Sligo County Council and its national counterparts, set policy and manage implementation. In parallel, informal networks of community stakeholders play an important complementary role, offering local knowledge, enhancing accountability, and ensuring that marginalised voices are not excluded.

Functional interdependencies are visible across the ecosystem. For example, while ATU contributes technical expertise, its outputs rely on local government facilitation for deployment. Likewise, the Council's success in community outreach depends on the credibility and presence of NGOs and grassroots initiatives.

Despite progress, gaps remain in equity and access. Rural and elderly populations, as well as some coastal communities, face barriers to sustained engagement. To address this, the LL has integrated visual and narrative communication tools, targeted outreach to farming and tourism sectors, and deliberate inclusion of affected groups in the co-design process.

Methodology and Typology

Stakeholders were identified and classified using a combination of:

- Desk research on institutional roles and mandates;
- Bilateral meetings and interviews with public and community actors;
- Workshops using system mapping and co-creation techniques;
- Typology based on stakeholder function: decision-maker, implementer, knowledge provider, supporter, and affected party.

A power-interest matrix was applied to assess influence levels and adaptive capacity, ensuring balanced representation in all phases of the LL. These actors are engaged through structured LL mechanisms including public workshops, policy dialogues, co-design sessions, and targeted local events. Their ongoing involvement is essential to ensuring that pilot actions are grounded in local knowledge, widely supported, and institutionally sustainable. The LL will continue to refine engagement strategies throughout the subsequent phases of the project.

Focal Action Situation (FAS)

The Focal Action Situation (FAS) in the Sligo Living Lab (LL) addresses the growing climate vulnerability of Ireland's northwest coastal region, where intensified erosion, sea-level rise, and storm events intersect with ecological fragility and competing land-use pressures. This situation presents both a strategic challenge and an opportunity to implement ecosystem-based adaptation (EbA) through inclusive, community-oriented processes.

Territorial and Socio-Ecological Stressors

Sligo's coastal ecosystems—including dune systems, wetlands, and peatlands—play a critical role in buffering against climate hazards such as flooding and storm surges. However, these ecosystems are under increasing strain due to sea-level rise, urban expansion, and storm-related damage. For example, erosion events following severe storms, including the damage to dunes in 2011, have demonstrated the urgency of adaptive interventions.

These environmental stressors are compounded by diverging stakeholder priorities between conservation, development, and tourism, often leading to tension in spatial planning and resource management. Fragmented governance, limited long-term funding, and inconsistencies in community engagement further reduce the effectiveness of local climate responses.

Entry Points for Co-Creation and Adaptation

In response, the Sligo LL has prioritised several entry points to facilitate systemic change:

- **Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EbA):** Ongoing projects in reforestation, wetland restoration, and peatland rewetting (e.g., *The Stranger*, *The Moor*, and *Strandville*) aim to restore natural defences and enhance ecological resilience.
- **Smart and Participatory Governance:** The LL fosters structured collaboration among Sligo County Council, Atlantic Technological University (ATU), environmental bodies, and citizens, with the aim of improving alignment across governance scales.
- **Technology-Enabled Monitoring:** Smart sensors and data-driven planning tools support real-time environmental tracking and strengthen early-warning and mitigation capabilities.
- **Community Stewardship and Climate Literacy:** Engagement activities—targeting schools, residents, and local NGOs—build trust, raise awareness, and support behavioural change linked to ecosystem protection and land-use practices.
- **Policy Integration:** The LL ensures that pilot actions align with the Sligo County Council Climate Action Plan 2024–2029, Ireland's Climate Action and Low Carbon Development Act (2022), and regional resilience objectives.

Systemic Framing and Theory of Change Alignment

The FAS has been developed in line with the PRO-CLIMATE Theory of Change and draws on both scientific expertise and local knowledge.

- **Inputs:** Local stakeholder insights, governance diagnostics (WP4), behavioural science from WP3, and technical contributions from ATU and other LL partners.
- **Processes:** Multi-criteria analysis, co-creation workshops, and nature-based solution prototyping, informed by prior work under the SCORE project.
- **Outputs:** Pilot interventions in coastal defence and dune restoration, community education programmes, and digital monitoring tools.

- **Outcomes:** Improved cooperation between sectors, strengthened ecosystem functions, and enhanced participatory governance at the county level.
- **Impacts:** Institutionalisation of EbA practices, increased climate literacy, and a replicable adaptation model suitable for other coastal communities in Ireland and beyond.

The Sligo LL demonstrates how a place-based, participatory approach can mobilise diverse actors and institutions around a shared adaptation agenda. By grounding pilot activities in both ecological understanding and behavioural insight, it provides a framework for transforming local challenges into long-term resilience strategies.

Behavioural and Institutional Barriers

The Sligo Living Lab addresses a series of behavioural and institutional barriers that inhibit climate adaptation in coastal areas. These include governance fragmentation, limited public understanding of environmental risks, and the absence of inclusive decision-making platforms. The LL uses participatory and data-informed approaches to overcome these obstacles and foster system-wide transformation (Table 28).

Table 28. Dimensions Addressing Behavioural and Institutional Barriers in the Sligo Living Lab

Dimension	Focus	Key Contributions
Co-Creation	Community-led design and ecosystem stewardship	Deployed environmental sensors; co-created solutions via workshops, games, and storytelling formats
Institutional Transformation	Mainstreaming EbA in public policy and planning	Partnered with Sligo County Council, CARO, NPWS, and ATU; aligned with national and EU frameworks
Behavioural Change	Supporting awareness and risk-informed decisions	Delivered outreach through Smart EARTH Hub; developed indicators with WP4 to assess behavioural shifts
Local Empowerment	Strengthening leadership and engagement among affected communities	Enabled local champions to advocate for EbA; involved schools, NGOs, and residents in co-monitoring

By addressing these barriers systematically, the Sligo LL provides a foundation for inclusive and effective adaptation. The model promotes civic trust, strengthens institutions, and enhances the region’s capacity to respond to climate change through collaborative and ecosystem-based strategies.

Phase 2: Ideate & Co-Design

Following the stakeholder mapping and contextual assessment conducted in Phase 1, the Sligo Living Lab (LL) advanced to the co-design phase with the organisation of an in-person workshop in September 2024. This step marked the transition from problem identification to the collaborative design of place-based adaptation responses, engaging local authorities, residents, academic partners, and civil society.

Objectives of the Co-Design Process

The workshop aimed to develop a shared understanding of priority risks and to translate these into realistic and locally grounded climate adaptation objectives. Participants included representatives from Sligo County Council, Atlantic Technological University (ATU), the Office of Public Works (OPW), the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), NGOs, and community actors including coastal residents and tourism stakeholders.

The workshop focused on:

- Identifying feasible responses to coastal erosion and flood risks;

- Exploring the use of ecosystem-based adaptation (EbA) and smart technologies in local pilot actions;
- Establishing preliminary pilot themes and actions to be tested in the upcoming implementation phase.

Stakeholder Engagement and Methods

Facilitated through interactive formats—such as serious games, visual storytelling, citizen panels, and thematic group discussions—the co-design workshop placed particular emphasis on inclusivity and local relevance. The process built on tools tested in previous initiatives and ensured a balance of perspectives across the quadruple helix sectors. Special attention was given to involving groups historically less engaged in environmental planning, including rural residents, landowners, and small tourism operators.

Participants discussed a range of topics, including:

- Gaps in data availability and environmental monitoring;
- Opportunities for local engagement in sensor-based co-monitoring;
- Mechanisms for knowledge exchange and feedback between institutions and communities.

Behavioural insights provided by WP3, including the use of social-ecological system (SES) frameworks and stakeholder typologies, helped guide discussions on behavioural tipping points and drivers for action. WP4 contributed initial indicators for evaluating inclusiveness and knowledge uptake.

Emerging Themes and Pilot Focus Areas

The co-design process led to the identification of three key areas for pilot implementation (Table 29). These were shaped through the workshop, bilateral meetings, and feedback gathered during community engagement activities.

Table 29. Focus areas emerged from the ideation process

Focus Area	Specific Pilot Activities
1. Nature-Based Coastal Protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-design and implementation of dune restoration projects - Deployment of smart sensors and community-led monitoring - Public engagement through beach stewardship initiatives
2. Smart Climate Monitoring and Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pilot use of low-cost environmental sensors and digital twin tools - Develop user-friendly visual communication tools for data sharing - Strengthen science-policy linkages at the local level
3. Inclusive Community Engagement and Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outreach to marginalised and underrepresented groups - Development of school-based environmental programmes - Creative campaigns promoting awareness and behavioural change

These pilot areas reflect Sligo’s core vulnerabilities—coastal erosion, biodiversity loss, and community disengagement—as well as opportunities for transformation through innovation and co-creation. The selected areas align with Ireland’s Climate Action Plan, regional policy priorities, and the broader goals of the PRO-CLIMATE project.

Outcomes and Next Steps

The co-design workshop marked a milestone in the Sligo LL process, setting the foundation for pilot implementation. Key outcomes include:

- **Consolidated Vision:** A jointly agreed pathway towards increased coastal resilience based on EbA and citizen participation;
- **Stakeholder Mobilisation:** Activation of a broad network of institutional and community actors;
- **Priority Setting:** Selection of three interlinked pilot themes tailored to the socio-ecological context of Sligo;
- **Commitment to Action:** Agreement among stakeholders to collaborate on pilot design, monitoring, and evaluation.

The LL will now move into the Prototype & Pilot phase, prioritising:

- Final definition of pilot sites and implementing partners;
- Development of key performance indicators in collaboration with WP4, with a focus on behavioural change, inclusiveness, and nature-based outcomes;
- Integration of insights from WP3 to monitor engagement and effectiveness of interventions;
- Embedding pilots within the Sligo County Council Climate Action Plan (2024–2029) to ensure continuity and upscaling potential.

The Sligo Living Lab continues to position itself as a model for inclusive and adaptive coastal governance. Through sustained co-creation, local knowledge integration, and digital innovation, it supports a long-term transition towards climate resilience and ecosystem health in Ireland's coastal communities.

Phase 3: Prototype & Pilot

The Prototype & Pilot phase of the Sligo Living Lab (LL) marks a pivotal moment in the operationalisation of co-designed adaptation strategies. Building on the outputs of earlier participatory phases, this stage transitions the Living Lab from conceptual planning to tangible field implementation. The focus is on addressing climate vulnerabilities in Sligo's coastal areas—particularly those related to dune erosion, coastal flooding, and declining ecosystem integrity—through real-world testing of nature-based, community-supported, and behaviourally informed interventions.

This phase is directly guided by the PRO-CLIMATE Theory of Change, which emphasises system-level resilience, behavioural transformation, and participatory governance. The pilot interventions aim not only to demonstrate technical viability but also to validate their social acceptability and institutional integration, with particular attention to inclusive engagement and long-term replicability.

Pilot Strategy and Methodological Framing

The Sligo LL has selected pilot sites in high-exposure coastal zones, including Streedagh Beach, Dunmorán Strand, and Enniscrone. These locations were chosen based on stakeholder input, ecological sensitivity, and potential for collaborative action. The pilot process includes:

- Co-design and co-implementation of ecosystem-based adaptation (EbA) solutions;
- Deployment of participatory monitoring tools;
- Public engagement formats tailored to the needs and preferences of diverse local actors.

The pilot design and monitoring are coordinated by Atlantic Technological University (ATU) Sligo and Sligo County Council, with support from other PRO-CLIMATE work packages—particularly WP2 (operational planning), WP3 (behavioural insights), WP4 (governance KPIs), and WP6 (scaling and policy integration).

Pilot Implementation Themes and Components

The pilot actions are grouped into three strategic focus areas, reflecting the outcomes of Phase 2 workshops and the LL's alignment with PRO-CLIMATE objectives (Table 30).

Table 30. Pilot Implementation Themes and Components – Sligo Living Lab

Focus Area	Pilot Objectives	Key Pilot Activities
1. Ecosystem-Based Coastal Adaptation	Implement community-driven nature-based solutions that reduce erosion and enhance ecosystem resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-design and implement dune protection and vegetation stabilisation actions - Use soft-engineering (e.g. brushwood, native planting) - Develop maintenance plans with schools and citizen groups
2. Behavioural Engagement for Climate Action	Promote behavioural shifts through participatory tools, climate literacy, and inclusive communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate awareness campaigns in collaboration with schools and NGOs - Storytelling and peer-to-peer outreach by trained community facilitators - Design and pilot community engagement formats using visual tools
3. Governance Innovation and Co-Monitoring	Strengthen adaptive local governance and embed inclusive co-monitoring in policy and planning frameworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deploy low-cost environmental sensors - Create accessible dashboards for erosion/flood data - Establish participatory data-sharing protocols with Sligo County Council

Institutional Roles and Change Agents

The pilot phase brings together a network of partners, each with a defined contribution:

- **ATU Sligo:** Technical coordination, monitoring design, and knowledge brokerage.
- **Sligo County Council:** Implementation lead, integration with local policies and services.
- **Local Communities:** Co-creators, testers, and communicators of pilot activities.
- **Change Agents:** Trained individuals (e.g. teachers, youth leaders, NGO staff) who support behavioural uptake and provide community-level feedback.

Through these partnerships, the LL promotes equity in voice and ownership—key principles of the PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab methodology.

Monitoring and Adaptive Learning

Ongoing monitoring and iterative evaluation are embedded throughout the pilot period. Using KPIs developed under WP4 and adapted to the local context, progress will be assessed along three dimensions:

- **Technical Effectiveness:** Efficacy of dune stabilisation, sensor performance, and data accuracy.

- **Behavioural Change:** Shifts in community awareness, engagement, and stewardship practices.
- **Governance Responsiveness:** Uptake of pilot learnings by public institutions and formal inclusion in planning processes.

Feedback mechanisms—including public debriefings, surveys, and learning circles—will support reflective adaptation of pilot actions during the implementation phase.

Expected Outcomes and Policy Alignment

The Sligo LL pilots are designed not only as proof-of-concept experiments, but as scalable components of a wider climate adaptation framework. Their outcomes are expected to contribute to:

- Enhanced physical resilience of coastal ecosystems and communities;
- Institutional learning on adaptive planning and public engagement;
- Policy feedback loops informing the Sligo County Climate Action Plan 2024–2029 and Ireland’s national adaptation pathways.

The pilot activities also support European ambitions under the EU Adaptation Strategy and the Green Deal, demonstrating how climate-vulnerable coastal areas can serve as innovation hubs for climate action.

Phase 4: Test & Evaluate

The final phase of the Sligo Living Lab (LL) centres on evaluating the performance, inclusiveness, and scalability of the co-created pilot interventions developed and implemented during earlier phases. This stage serves both as a mechanism for assessing impact and as a strategic step towards embedding the Living Lab model into local governance and long-term adaptation planning.

This phase addresses how behavioural, institutional, and environmental outcomes evolve through community-led experimentation. It aims to test what works, for whom, and under what conditions, ensuring the pilots remain contextually relevant, technically feasible, and socially acceptable.

The evaluation strategy applies a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative insights and quantitative data to assess the effectiveness of the pilots. Indicators have been developed by WP4, and reflect key behavioural and governance dimensions (Table 31).

Table 31. Monitoring, Risk Management, and Scaling Strategy – Sligo Living Lab

Category	Key Elements
Monitoring & KPIs	Informed by WP6 and WP4 indicators. Tracks climate literacy gains, community participation, uptake of digital tools, and institutional responsiveness to co-created actions.
Data Collection	Digital surveys, stakeholder interviews, community-led monitoring outputs, workshop feedback, and visual tools (e.g. mapping platforms, dashboards).
Risk Management	- Identified risks: participation fatigue, political turnover, limited uptake of digital tools - Adaptive responses: flexible engagement formats, use of local champions, integration with ongoing county-level initiatives
Review Mechanism	Biannual internal learning workshops, evaluation checkpoints with WP leads, community feedback forums.
Scaling Strategy	- Toolkits and replication guidelines for use in other Irish or EU coastal communities - Dissemination through PRO-CLIMATE networks and Irish adaptation fora

	- Policy linkage with Climate Action Plan 2024–2029, National Adaptation Framework, and CARO regional actions
Long-term Impact	Strengthens public engagement in local adaptation; promotes shared ownership of ecosystem-based solutions; supports institutional learning and builds adaptive capacity in governance systems.

The evaluation process does not merely quantify results—it helps generate strategic knowledge for scaling and transfer. Particular emphasis is placed on surfacing learning from failure, understanding behavioural dynamics, and refining participatory governance processes.

The outcomes of this phase will also inform national and EU policy dialogues, including knowledge-sharing through the PRO-CLIMATE dissemination channels. Evidence from Sligo will contribute to identifying success factors and conditions for replicability across other coastal and rural contexts in Europe.

By embedding evaluation into a broader cycle of reflexive learning and stakeholder co-ownership, this phase consolidates the Living Lab’s role as a permanent platform for adaptation innovation. It positions Sligo as a demonstrator for citizen-led, ecosystem-based, and digitally enabled responses to climate risk.

Conclusion

The Sligo Living Lab (LL) represents a place-based, forward-looking approach to climate adaptation in a rural and coastal Irish context. Anchored in the PRO-CLIMATE Theory of Change, the LL combines ecosystem-based adaptation, digital innovation, and inclusive stakeholder engagement to respond to the region’s increasing exposure to climate risks such as coastal erosion, flooding, and extreme weather variability.

This Pilot Operational Plan (POP) outlines a structured, four-phase methodology—**Empathise & Define, Ideate & Co-Design, Prototype & Pilot, and Test & Evaluate**—to guide the co-development and testing of locally appropriate solutions. These interventions have focused on nature-based coastal protection, smart monitoring, and community capacity-building, with a strong emphasis on integration into existing local governance frameworks and planning instruments.

The LL has successfully mobilised a wide spectrum of actors, including Sligo County Council, Atlantic Technological University (ATU), national agencies, environmental NGOs, and local residents. It has also created entry points for underrepresented groups—such as small-scale landowners and coastal households—to participate in shaping adaptation strategies. This inclusive approach enhances both legitimacy and the sustainability of actions.

By leveraging digital tools, citizen science, and knowledge co-production, the LL has fostered conditions for behavioural change, strengthened governance coordination, and enabled the practical testing of pilot interventions in real-world coastal settings. The active collaboration with technical partners and the embedding of PRO-CLIMATE indicators ensure that results are both measurable and transferable.

As the Living Lab enters the final phase of implementation, it brings forward insights and tested practices that can inform climate adaptation efforts in similar regions across Ireland and Europe. Its contribution lies not only in delivering technical solutions, but also in modelling how rural and coastal communities can lead systemic adaptation through participatory innovation and integrated planning.

The Sligo LL provides a replicable pathway for advancing climate resilience—one rooted in ecological stewardship, digital capability, and collective action.

Annex 6 Bergen Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan

Introduction

The Bergen Living Lab (LL), developed within the Horizon Europe PRO-CLIMATE project, is conceived as a regional innovation platform to support sustainable land-use governance and inclusive climate adaptation in Vestland County, Norway. Drawing on behavioural insights, participatory governance, and systemic approaches, this Pilot Operational Plan (POP) outlines an initial framework for co-creating regionally grounded responses to biodiversity loss, land-use pressure, and emerging climate risks.

Located in one of the fastest-developing regions of Norway, Vestland has experienced significant ecological change over recent years. Between 2017 and 2022, over **44,000 small-scale land-use decisions** were recorded, contributing to the estimated loss of **79 square metres of nature every minute**—a dynamic that has accelerated the so-called "nature crisis" as Norwegian Environment Agency revealed in 2023. Bergen, as the county's largest city, reflects both the pressures and potential for aligning urban development with sustainability goals, especially in relation to coastal adaptation, land-use planning, and nature-based solutions (NbS).

The LL is **coordinated by the University of Bergen**, with internal contributions from the Centre for Climate and Energy Transformation (CET). While broader stakeholder collaboration—including with municipal authorities, regional planners, environmental NGOs, and energy providers—is **still at an exploratory stage**, initial outreach activities and informal exchanges have begun to identify shared priorities. The current focus lies on **building trust, clarifying mutual goals**, and setting the stage for more formal co-creation processes in future phases.

This POP sets out a structured yet adaptive roadmap for implementing the PRO-CLIMATE Living Lab methodology across four core phases: *Empathise & Define*, *Ideate & Co-Design*, *Prototype & Pilot*, and *Test & Evaluate*. While the LL is formally referred to as the "Bergen Living Lab," its intended geographic scope extends to Vestland County, acknowledging the region's complex socio-ecological dynamics and the need for both urban and rural integration.

By embedding climate adaptation in land-use planning and fostering inclusive engagement mechanisms, the Bergen LL aims to provide a regionally tailored, replicable model for transformative governance in the face of accelerating environmental change.

Clarification on Scope and Applicability

Although this document is titled the *Bergen Living Lab Pilot Operational Plan*—in alignment with the naming used in the PRO-CLIMATE Grant Agreement—the applicability and operational focus of the Living Lab extends beyond the city of Bergen to encompass the broader **Vestland County**. The activities, stakeholder engagements, and systemic interventions proposed herein are designed to reflect the interconnected socio-ecological and governance dynamics of Vestland, including its municipalities, regional institutions, and civil society organisations. While Bergen serves as a central node within this network, the Living Lab's ambition is to foster inclusive and regionally relevant pathways for sustainable climate adaptation across Vestland, building synergies between urban and rural actors.

Phase 1: Empathise & Define

Contextual Diagnosis

The Bergen Living Lab (LL), as part of the Horizon Europe PRO-CLIMATE project, operates within a dynamic and decentralised governance landscape in western Norway. While referred to as the "Bergen LL" in line with the PRO-CLIMATE Grant Agreement, the scope of activities and relevance of the Lab extend to **Vestland County**, encompassing both urban and rural municipalities whose land-use trajectories are increasingly interlinked.

The region is marked by strong environmental governance frameworks and public awareness of sustainability issues. However, ongoing **land-use pressures, climate-related risks, and**

fragmented governance structures pose barriers to effective climate adaptation. A preliminary co-creation workshop, conducted in early 2024, brought together a limited group of civil society actors, students, and NGOs. These early discussions revealed both enthusiasm for participation and challenges in mobilising broader institutional engagement.

Environmental stressors include a **rise in average temperatures, increased annual precipitation**, and growing risk of **flooding and biodiversity loss**. The cumulative impact of dispersed land-use decisions—such as incremental development of green areas—continues to undermine conservation objectives and erode public trust in planning processes.

Meanwhile, socio-economic factors present both opportunities and constraints. While the region benefits from strong economic indicators and high levels of education and employment, engagement remains **uneven across stakeholder groups**, particularly for small-scale actors such as rural communities, leisure users, and informal environmental networks. These groups often perceive limited influence in formal decision-making, despite their environmental knowledge and legal rights to participation.

The governance structure is shaped by decentralised planning authority, with **municipalities and counties holding significant discretion**. While this supports local autonomy, it also contributes to **variability in adaptation efforts**, coordination gaps across levels of governance, and difficulties in balancing competing policy goals such as housing, renewable energy, and nature conservation (Table 32).

Table 32. Key Contextual Challenges in the Bergen Living Lab

Category	Key Issues
Environmental Pressures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased precipitation and warming trends intensify flood risks and ecological degradation. - Dispersed land-use changes challenge green space protection. - Infrastructure expansion adds pressure on coastal and inland ecosystems.
Socio-Economic Dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong socio-economic baseline masks gaps in participation from less-institutionalised groups. - Underrepresentation of rural actors, small businesses, and civil society in spatial planning processes.
Governance Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conflicting planning priorities between development and conservation. - Decentralisation without strong vertical coordination. - Structural barriers to inclusive engagement, despite formal equality frameworks.

While still at an early stage, the Bergen LL is positioned to explore how **co-creation methodologies and behavioural insights** can be adapted to the Norwegian context. Initial findings point to significant communication and engagement barriers, particularly across governance levels. The LL currently functions as an exploratory space for scoping stakeholder dynamics and initiating structured dialogue.

Opportunities for Systemic Change

Early observations and engagement activities have identified the following strategic areas for further development:

- **Integrated Land-Use Governance:** Facilitating coordination between municipal and regional actors could help address tensions between infrastructure development and ecosystem protection. Co-creation may provide a platform to support better alignment across sectors.

- **Inclusive Stakeholder Engagement:** Future engagement efforts should move beyond formal consultation requirements, aiming to meaningfully include **less-institutionalised and community-based actors**, such as rural land users and environmental volunteers.
- **Behavioural Change for Adaptation:** The application of behavioural tools and participatory models can support **shared ownership** of adaptation strategies. A digital **climate adaptation model** developed under PRO-CLIMATE will be tested in upcoming workshops to support practical engagement with planners and citizens.
- **Policy Alignment and Local Autonomy:** Norway's decentralised governance allows for adaptation strategies to be tailored to local needs. The LL can explore how regional aspirations in Vestland align with national climate targets while respecting municipal priorities and legitimacy.

As the Bergen Living Lab progresses, the focus will remain on **expanding institutional participation**, strengthening communication channels, and applying practical tools to support collaborative planning. Upcoming digital workshops will provide a testing ground for new engagement formats and may serve as a catalyst for scaling the Living Lab's relevance across Vestland County.

Stakeholder Mapping

Stakeholder mapping in the Bergen Living Lab (LL) reflects the distributed and multi-level nature of Norway's climate governance system. Using the Quadruple Helix framework, the mapping exercise identifies a range of actors from public authorities, academic institutions, civil society, and the private sector—each contributing to, or being affected by, climate adaptation efforts within Vestland County.

The mapping was conducted through early-stage interviews, document review, and internal expertise from the University of Bergen. At this phase, stakeholder engagement remains limited, with formal participation from institutional actors still under development.

Identified Stakeholders and Their Roles

The current landscape reveals a set of key actors with varying degrees of involvement and influence:

- **Local and Regional Authorities:** Bergen Kommune and Vestland Fylke are responsible for spatial planning and environmental management. Øygarden and Askøy municipalities also hold relevant competencies in neighbouring coastal areas.
- **Research and Academic Institutions:** The University of Bergen, particularly through CET, provides knowledge on climate risk, land-use dynamics, and behavioural change. CET currently coordinates the LL and acts as a key knowledge partner and facilitator.
- **National Institutions:** Ministries such as Climate and Environment, and Energy and Petroleum, play overarching roles in policy guidance and regulation. Their involvement in the LL is indirect at this stage but relevant for future scaling.
- **Civil Society and NGOs:** Environmental organisations such as Naturvernforbundet are active in land-use debates and public awareness efforts. Their involvement in the LL so far has been through informal dialogue and one co-creation workshop.
- **Private Sector:** Large-scale infrastructure and energy actors like Equinor and Statnett are recognised stakeholders with relevance to land-use and environmental planning, though not yet formally engaged.
- **Media and Local Communities:** Regional media (e.g., NRK Vestland, Bergens Tidende) and resident groups influence discourse on planning and nature protection. Their engagement is foreseen as part of future communication and co-creation phases.

Governance Structures

The LL operates within a decentralised planning system where municipalities have strong autonomy. Vestland Fylke provides a regional coordination layer. However, collaboration across these levels is

often fragmented. While formal structures for participation exist, real engagement of non-institutional stakeholders remains limited.

The LL currently serves as a **facilitation space**, coordinated by the University of Bergen, with early outreach focused on building trust and exploring shared priorities. Institutional participation is expected to grow through upcoming workshops and modelling demonstrations under the PRO-CLIMATE framework.

Methodology and Typology

Stakeholder identification and classification were based on:

- **Desk review** of strategic and policy documents at municipal and regional levels;
- **Bilateral meetings** with academics, civil society, and selected municipal representatives;
- **Typology analysis** distinguishing stakeholders by role: decision-maker, knowledge provider, implementer, affected group, or supporter;
- **Power-Influence mapping** to understand proximity to the LL's focal issues.

The LL prioritises transparency and gradual inclusion, recognising that trust-building is a long-term process, particularly in contexts where stakeholder engagement has been uneven (Table 33).

Table 33. Summary of Stakeholders Engaged

Stakeholder Group	Examples	Role in the LL
Public Authorities	Bergen Kommune, Vestland Fylke	Planning, implementation, coordination
Academic Institutions	University of Bergen – CET	Knowledge partner, LL coordination
Civil Society & NGOs	Naturvernforbundet, other local environmental groups, Local associations, citizens	Awareness, advocacy, informal expertise
Private Sector	Equinor, Statnett,	Land-use impact, future engagement potential

The Bergen LL stakeholder mapping provides an initial overview of actor roles and relationships in climate adaptation planning. As the LL evolves, stakeholder involvement will be expanded and formalised through structured activities in the next phases of the PRO-CLIMATE methodology (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Bergen Living Lab Stakeholder Mapping based on the Quadruple Helix Model

Focal Action Situation (FAS)

The Bergen Living Lab (LL) focuses on the cumulative loss of natural areas linked to dispersed land-use changes—an issue increasingly framed as part of Norway's broader "nature crisis". This trend has raised concerns about biodiversity decline, weakened ecosystem services, and reduced climate resilience.

Territorial and Socio-Ecological Stressors

Bergen and the broader Vestland region are exposed to multiple environmental pressures, including increasing precipitation, rising temperatures, and growing urbanisation. These climatic stressors intersect with a complex governance landscape, where municipal autonomy, national infrastructure priorities, and local environmental values often collide.

Stakeholders have pointed to the fragmentation of planning processes and the challenges of balancing land development (e.g., for housing, energy, or aquaculture) with nature protection and long-term climate adaptation. Localised examples—such as pressure on the Lønnebakke forest and coastal wetlands—illustrate the consequences of cumulative land-use decisions taken without sufficient ecological foresight.

Systemic Framing and Strategic Entry Points

The Bergen LL frames the FAS around land-use governance and the potential for climate-smart spatial planning. Co-creation activities are being designed to support more coordinated, inclusive, and environmentally responsive development approaches across Vestland.

Inputs:

- Scientific and local knowledge on spatial planning, environmental pressures, and biodiversity.
- Media reports and stakeholder reflections from early LL activities and workshops.

Processes:

- Participatory mapping and scenario planning exercises.
- Pilot dialogues on zoning, cumulative impacts, and nature-based solutions (NbS).

Outputs:

- Proposed zoning reforms and experimental NbS installations.
- Stakeholder commitments to support transparent and participatory planning.

Outcomes:

- Improved engagement of civil society and non-institutional actors.
- Greater coherence between municipal and regional land-use strategies.

Impacts:

- A foundation for institutionalised participatory governance.
- Increased public trust in planning processes and greater resilience to land degradation and climate risks.

Behavioural and Institutional Barriers

The Bergen LL also addresses behavioural and institutional challenges related to planning and land-use management. These include gaps in cross-sector coordination, limited public participation in spatial decisions, and trade-offs between economic and ecological priorities (Table 34).

Table 34. Dimensions Addressing Key Barriers in the Bergen LL

Pillar	Focus	Key Contributions
Co-Creation	Participatory land-use governance	Co-design workshops with municipalities, communities, and researchers to identify trade-offs and adaptation pathways.
Institutional Transformation	Governance innovation	Collaboration with local planners to align climate goals with land-use practices, referencing existing tools like Bergen’s Green Strategy.
Behavioural Change	Planning literacy and responsibility	Stakeholder engagement on densification, biodiversity loss, and green infrastructure via workshops and behavioural insight methods.
Local Empowerment	Inclusion of non-institutional voices	Engagement of youth, NGOs, and community members in spatial dialogues and pilot design using hybrid (digital and in-person) methods.

By anchoring the FAS in the structural dynamics of land governance and the urgency of ecological degradation, the Bergen LL positions itself as a space for experimentation and learning. It aims to support more transparent and participatory planning models that integrate climate, biodiversity, and societal values—laying the groundwork for interventions that are both locally legitimate and systemically robust.

Phase 2: Ideate & Co-Design

Following the contextual diagnosis and stakeholder mapping in Phase 1, the Bergen Living Lab (LL) entered the Ideate & Co-Design phase in spring 2025. This stage marked the beginning of collaborative idea generation for adaptation strategies that align with Vestland’s complex land-use and climate governance landscape.

Objectives and Early Engagement

The first in-person co-creation workshop was held on 5 May 2025 in Bergen, organised by the University of Bergen in collaboration with Future Thinking. It brought together a modest but diverse group of participants, including civil society representatives, students, NGOs, researchers, and local planners. Conducted in Norwegian, the session aimed to:

- Open dialogue on regional land-use and climate adaptation challenges;
- Introduce the Living Lab methodology and its relevance for Vestland;
- Elicit initial feedback on governance gaps and opportunities for co-creation.

While formal institutional engagement is still developing, the workshop served as an important entry point. Further engagement activities are planned with stakeholders from Vestland County, municipal planning departments, and regional agencies during the upcoming digital workshops.

Methods and Emerging Themes

The co-design session applied inclusive facilitation methods, drawing on storytelling, small group dialogue, and behavioural insights developed under WP3. The aim was to encourage participants to reflect on climate-related land-use tensions and propose early ideas for collaborative adaptation.

Key themes identified during the workshop included:

- The potential of nature-based solutions (NbS) for biodiversity protection and urban flood mitigation;
- Fragmented planning structures that limit inter-agency coordination;
- A need for stronger communication between science, planning, and public stakeholders to support long-term adaptation goals.

The workshop also validated behavioural barriers identified in WP3, including psychological distance from climate risks and low public trust in decision-making processes.

Behavioural and Governance Integration

Inputs from WP3 and WP4 helped shape the design of the session and guide the initial identification of behavioural indicators. These included stakeholder diversity in engagement, interest alignment, and communication openness. WP4 also supported the formulation of preliminary KPIs for inclusivity, trust-building, and coordination across planning authorities.

A digital climate adaptation modelling tool developed by the University of Bergen will be introduced during a follow-up workshop in June 2025. This tool aims to stimulate structured dialogue and support participatory scenario planning around zoning, biodiversity, and infrastructure trade-offs.

Focus Areas Emerging from Co-Design

Based on insights from the May workshop and supporting analysis, the Bergen LL identified three provisional areas to guide pilot development (Table 35). These reflect both immediate local priorities and broader systemic challenges in spatial governance and adaptation.

Table 35. Focus Areas Emerging from the Ideation Process

Focus Area	Specific Pilot Activities
1. Sustainable Urban Land-Use Planning and Nature-Based Solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Promote participatory planning mechanisms that integrate NbS and biodiversity corridors; – Map and prioritise green spaces for conservation in municipal land-use strategies; – Explore practical tools for NbS integration in urban zoning.

<p>2. Inclusive and Participatory Climate Governance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Establish collaborative land-use forums involving government, NGOs, youth, and academia; – Use visual tools and deliberative methods to engage underrepresented groups; – Co-create land-use policy scenarios reflecting diverse stakeholder priorities.
<p>3. Institutional Innovation for Resilient Infrastructure</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Test inter-agency coordination models for infrastructure planning (e.g. energy and transport projects); – Align regional climate goals with zoning and permitting procedures through pilot planning charters.

These focus areas reflect structural governance challenges in Vestland and Norway more broadly—such as decentralised authority, land-use conflicts, and stakeholder asymmetries—and provide a foundation for piloting in Phase 3.

Outcomes and Next Steps

This early co-design phase established a collaborative foundation for upcoming interventions. Key achievements include:

- **Stakeholder Activation:** Engagement of key groups including CET at the University of Bergen, youth organisations, NGOs such as Naturvernforbundet, and select municipal planners;
- **Challenge Framing:** Validation of barriers to institutional alignment, trust, and knowledge integration;
- **Initial Pilot Support:** Expression of interest from Øygarden Kommune and others to participate in pilot planning processes.

Next steps include:

- Finalising pilot themes and confirming roles for co-lead stakeholders;
- Refining KPIs for monitoring engagement, governance coordination, and adaptation learning with support from WP4 (Deliverable 4.2);
- Testing the modelling tool as a facilitation mechanism during the digital workshop in June;
- Developing a transparent communication plan to reinforce legitimacy and stakeholder commitment.

By structuring its co-design phase around inclusivity, behavioural insight, and institutional reflexivity, the Bergen LL is preparing to develop targeted pilot actions that respond to the complex socio-ecological realities of Vestland. These pilots aim to demonstrate how participatory governance and systems thinking can improve both the quality and legitimacy of land-use adaptation in the context of Norway’s climate and biodiversity challenges

Phase 3: Prototype & Pilot

The Prototype & Pilot phase of the Bergen Living Lab (LL) is foreseen as the next stage of development within the PRO-CLIMATE framework. It will mark the transition from exploratory engagement to the first cycle of applied experimentation, where co-identified ideas will be tested through small-scale interventions that explore climate-related land-use challenges in Vestland County. While this phase has not yet been implemented, preliminary steps have been taken to lay the groundwork for future piloting activities.

Following the first co-creation workshop held in May 2025—focused primarily on engaging civil society stakeholders—the LL is preparing to broaden its reach through a second series of digital workshops in mid-2025. These sessions aim to involve municipal and regional institutions such as

Bergen Kommune, Øygarden, and Vestland Fylke, whose collaboration is essential for moving forward with pilot development and validation.

Pilot Strategy and Concept Preparation

At this preparatory stage, several thematic directions have emerged based on stakeholder dialogues and academic analysis. These are not fixed commitments, but rather starting points for testing feasibility, stimulating discussion, and identifying institutional interest. Proposed directions include:

- **Green Zoning Concepts:** Exploring how biodiversity and ecosystem services could be integrated into land-use decisions through participatory planning tools.
- **Nature-Based Solutions (NbS):** Identifying candidate sites and co-design approaches for flood mitigation and urban greening projects.
- **Participatory Scenario Mapping:** Piloting digital and physical tools for visualising alternative land-use trajectories and stakeholder trade-offs.
- **Behavioural Nudges for Sustainable Lifestyles:** Developing light interventions focused on mobility, awareness of urban nature, or adaptive behaviours related to land use.

These concepts will be refined through stakeholder dialogue, particularly using upcoming modelling demonstrations and feedback loops coordinated by the University of Bergen team (Table 36).

Table 36. Pilot Implementation Strategy and Key Operational Components

Section	Title	Key Elements
Institutional Coordination	Urban governance interface	To be developed with municipal and regional authorities, under the coordination of the University of Bergen
Role of Change Agents	Climate facilitators	Civil society representatives, planners, and researchers acting as connectors and local multipliers
Focus Areas for Piloting	Behavioural and spatial levers	Participatory zoning, NbS concepts, mobility and land-use awareness pilots
Strategic Alignment & Impact	Policy coherence	To align with national climate adaptation policies and Bergen's local strategies

Looking Ahead: Modelling Tool and Stakeholder Activation

An important catalyst for this phase will be the demonstration of a new climate adaptation modelling tool, developed within the PRO-CLIMATE project. This tool is intended to visualise spatial dynamics and facilitate informed decision-making. Its presentation at the upcoming digital workshops will serve as both a content anchor and a mechanism for attracting institutional engagement.

Through this tool, stakeholders will be invited to explore scenarios and assess how proposed pilot ideas align with regional priorities and climate targets. The modelling tool is expected to play a key role in shaping the pilots under WP5 and establishing a shared platform for collaborative governance.

Outlook and Next Steps

Although not yet underway, the Prototype & Pilot phase represents a critical step in the evolution of the Bergen LL. It will be activated once stakeholder readiness, institutional interest, and co-developed ideas are sufficiently aligned. The goals of this phase include:

- Testing the operational space for land-use innovation and participatory planning;
- Enhancing trust between institutions, researchers, and civil society actors;
- Creating scalable and locally relevant pilot models that inform the LL's contribution to systemic change.

By setting the stage for future experimentation, this phase will determine whether the Bergen LL can mature into a robust platform for inclusive, climate-resilient urban governance in Vestland.

Phase 4: Test & Evaluate

The fourth phase of the Bergen Living Lab (LL) focuses on initiating a formative evaluation of early concepts, tools, and engagement pathways, while preparing the ground for structured piloting in the second half of 2025. Given the LL's current exploratory stage—anchored in an initial co-creation workshop held in May 2025 with civil society and academic actors—this phase prioritises feedback collection, institutional readiness assessment, and refinement of Living Lab methodologies.

Broader engagement with municipal and regional authorities, including planners from Bergen Kommune and representatives of Vestland County, is anticipated through digital workshops scheduled for mid-2025. These workshops will play a key role in testing the relevance and applicability of the Living Lab's tools—particularly the climate adaptation modelling tool currently under development within WP5.

Objectives and Focus Areas

The key aims of this phase are to:

- Test the functionality and engagement potential of the modelling tool as a decision-support resource for urban and regional planning;
- Assess initial stakeholder responses to proposed planning scenarios and behavioural interventions;
- Identify institutional enablers and constraints for scaling co-created land-use adaptation strategies.

Rather than a summative evaluation, this phase introduces an iterative learning cycle where feedback from participants will help to shape and validate future interventions (Table 37).

Table 37. Monitoring, Risk Management, and Scaling Strategy for the Bergen LL

Category	Key Elements
Monitoring & KPIs	Indicators informed by WP4 and local plans such as <i>Grønn Strategi</i> and <i>Sirkulære Bergen</i> ; initial tracking of participation, inclusion, and planning responsiveness.
Data Collection & Analysis	Mixed-method approach, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Feedback from workshops and modelling sessions – Policy and planning document reviews – Logs from bilateral meetings and stakeholder reflections
Risk Management	Identified risks include low institutional responsiveness, policy misalignment, and resource constraints. Mitigation strategies include adaptive workshop formats, informal liaison building, and involvement of “planning ambassadors” in key institutions.
Review Mechanism	Internal quarterly reviews with UiB and PRO-CLIMATE WP leads, combined with reflection workshops involving municipal staff and community actors.
Scaling Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Strengthen links with ongoing regional plans (<i>Grønn Strategi</i>, EU Mission on Adaptation) – Identify transferable methods for other Nordic or EU regions – Develop guidance for embedding LL approaches into formal spatial planning routines

Long-term Impact	Supports inclusive and adaptive governance; enhances cross-sectoral trust; offers a replicable model for participatory spatial planning aligned with the EU Green Deal and SDGs.
-------------------------	--

Forward Outlook

This phase acts as a transitional space between exploratory engagement and operational pilot implementation. It allows the Bergen LL to refine its approach, test its tools, and assess institutional appetite for co-developed land-use interventions. The findings will directly inform the next iteration of stakeholder workshops and modelling demonstrations planned for autumn 2025.

By taking an adaptive and formative approach, this phase contributes to building a shared vision among actors involved in climate-resilient land use in Vestland. The Bergen LL continues to position itself as a regional testbed for collaborative planning and sustainable urban transformation, with potential to shape broader policy debates and cross-border knowledge exchange across the PRO-CLIMATE network.

Conclusion

The Bergen Living Lab (LL), developed within the PRO-CLIMATE project, serves as an emerging space for collaborative exploration of climate adaptation and sustainable land-use governance in Vestland County, Norway. While referred to as the “Bergen LL” in project documentation, the scope of activity extends beyond the city of Bergen to include a broader regional focus on the challenges and opportunities facing both urban and rural planning contexts.

This Pilot Operational Plan (POP) outlines the early stages of an adaptive, co-creative process designed to build shared understanding, foster stakeholder collaboration, and prepare for the prototyping of regionally grounded interventions. Initial activities—including a first co-creation workshop in May 2025 and bilateral meetings with civil society and academic actors—have laid the foundation for broader institutional engagement, expected to progress through digital workshops and follow-up interactions in the months ahead.

A key priority moving forward is the demonstration and iterative refinement of a climate adaptation modelling tool, developed under WP5. This tool will be introduced during the upcoming sessions and is intended to support participatory planning, inform spatial governance decisions, and facilitate cross-sector dialogue. Its piloting is expected to strengthen the Living Lab’s practical relevance and attract further interest from municipal and regional planning authorities.

While formalised institutional support and inter-agency coordination are still evolving, the LL has successfully initiated early collaborations with researchers, environmental NGOs, and selected local actors. The proposed pilot directions—such as participatory planning forums, nature-based zoning concepts, and institutional coordination mechanisms—will be refined and validated through continued stakeholder engagement and feedback.

Operating within Norway’s decentralised governance system, the Bergen LL reflects both the opportunities and the challenges of advancing systemic change in a pluralistic planning environment. Emphasis is placed on inclusivity, trust-building, and iterative learning—recognising that transformation in this context requires sustained commitment and careful alignment with institutional mandates.

As it develops, the Bergen Living Lab contributes to the wider PRO-CLIMATE network by offering regionally specific insights into co-creation methodologies, behavioural engagement, and climate-adaptive planning. It provides a promising platform for experimentation, enabling knowledge exchange and supporting the emergence of integrated, participatory, and future-oriented approaches to land use and climate resilience across Nordic regions and beyond.

Bibliography

- Anton, C., Liu, X., Tamiakis, I., Trochidis, I., Yendell, A., Nienaber, A.-M., . . . Theodorakopoulou, I. (2024). *Baseline Assessment and Knowledge Gathering for the PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs*. Retrieved from Zanodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/15131069>
- Amorim, E. E. R., Menezes, M., & Fernandes, K. V. (2022). Urban Living Labs and Critical Infrastructure. *2022 IEEE International Smart Cities Conference (ISC2)*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISC255366.2022.9922441>
- Arnold, R. D., & Wade, J. P. (2015). A Definition of Systems Thinking: A Systems Approach. *Procedia Computer Science*, *44*, 669–678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.03.050>
- Baccarne, B., Logghe, S., Schuurman, D., & De Marez, L. (2016). Governing Quintuple Helix Innovation: Urban Living Labs and Socio-Ecological Entrepreneurship. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, *6*(3), 22–30. <https://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/972>
- Ballon, P., Schuurman, D., & Blackman, C. (2015). *Living Labs: Concepts, Tools and Cases*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Brown, T. (2009). *Change by Design: How Design Thinking Transforms Organizations and Inspires Innovation* (1st ed). HarperCollins Publishers.
- Calzada, I., & Cowie, P. (2017). Beyond Smart and Data-Driven City-Regions? Rethinking Stakeholder-Helices Strategies. *Regions Magazine*, *308*(4), 25–28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13673882.2017.11958675>
- Commission, E. (2016). *Guidelines on project implementation*.
- Committee of the Regions. Commission for Social Policy Education, E. R., Culture., Progress Consulting S.r.l., & Fondazione FORMIT Italy. (2016). *Using the quadruple helix approach to accelerate the transfer of research and innovation results to regional growth*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2863/408040>
- Compagnucci, L., Spigarelli, F., Coelho, J., & Duarte, C. (2021). Living Labs and user engagement for innovation and sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, *289*, 125721. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125721>
- Eriksson, M., Niitamo, V. P., Kulkki, S., Hribernik, K. A., & Schuurman, D. (2005). State-of-the-art in living labs. *CISTEMa Working Paper*, *29*.
- Fischer, F. (2000). Citizen participation and the democratization of policy expertise: From theoretical inquiry to practical cases. *Policy Sciences*, *33*(1), 155–165.
- Freeman, L. C. (2004). *The development of social network analysis: a study in the sociology of science*. Empirical Press.
- Friedman, A. L., & Miles, S. (2010). *Stakeholders: theory and practice* (Nachdr.). Oxford Univ. Press.
- Geels, F. W. (2002). Technological transitions as evolutionary reconfiguration processes: a multi-level perspective and a case-study. *Research Policy*, *31*(8–9), 1257–1274.
- Marvin, S., Bulkeley, H., Mai, L., McCormick, K., & Palgan, Y. V. (Eds.). (2018). *Urban living labs: experimenting with city futures*. Routledge, an imprint of the Taylor & Francis Group.
- McKenzie-Mohr, D. (2011). *Fostering Sustainable Behavior: An Introduction to Community-Based Social Marketing*. New Society Publishers.
- Moore, M. L. (2017a). System change, not personal change: Why we need to shift our focus to the social determinants of unhealthy behaviors. *American Journal of Public Health*, *107*(8), 1189–1191.
- Moore, M. L. (2017b). System change, not personal change: Why we need to shift our focus to the social determinants of unhealthy behaviors. *American Journal of Public Health*, *107*(8), 1189–1191.

- Nienaber, A.-M., Spundflasch, S., & Soares, A. E. S. (2023). *Behavioural change in local authorities to increase organisational capacity*. In G. Marsden, A. Nikolaeva, & D. Milakis (Eds.), *Capacity building in local authorities for sustainable transport planning* (pp. 135–151). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-1670-8_9
- Nienaber, A.-M., Soares, A. E. S., Woodcock, A., & Spundflasch, S. (2019). *Sustainable urban mobility in Europe: Implementation needs behavioural change* (Policy Brief No. 3). Horizon 2020 SUITS Project. https://www.suits-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/SUITS_PolicyBrief3.pdf
- Puerari, E., De Koning, J. I. J. C., Von Wirth, T., Karré, P. M., Mulder, I. J., & Loorbach, D. A. (2018). Co-Creation Dynamics in Urban Living Labs. *Sustainability*, 10(6), 1893. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10061893>
- Reed, M. S. (2008). Stakeholder participation for environmental management: a literature review. *Biological Conservation*, 141(10), 2417–2431.
- Sanders, E. B.-N., & Stappers, P. J. (2008). Co-creation and the new landscapes of design. *CoDesign*, 4(1), 5–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15710880701875068>
- Schuurman, D., & Tönurist, P. (2017a). Co-creation at the heart of modern living labs. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 7(11), 22–32.
- Schuurman, D., & Tönurist, P. (2017b). Co-creation at the heart of modern living labs. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 7(11), 22–32.
- Ståhlbröst, A. (2012). *A living lab as a methodology for innovation and development* (Issue VR 2012: 02). Vinnova.
- Thorne, C., Evans, E., & Penning-Rowsell, E. (2009). *Future flooding and coastal erosion risks*. Thomas Telford Ltd.
- Tomaszewski, L. E., Zarestky, J., & Gonzalez, E. (2020). Planning Qualitative Research: Design and Decision Making for New Researchers. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19, 1609406920967174. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406920967174>
- Waddock, S. (2001). Integrity and mindfulness: Foundations of responsible business. *Academy of Management Executive*, 15(2), 132–148.
- Weiss, C. H. (1995). Nothing as practical as good theory: evidence-based policy meets theory-based evaluation. *Evaluation Review*, 19(1), 79–106.
- Wright, C., Kiparoglou, V., Williams, M., & Hilton, J. (2012). A Framework for Resilience Thinking. *Procedia Computer Science*, 8, 45–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2012.01.012>